

Neutrosophic $\mathcal{N}$ -structures over UP-algebras

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Abstract: The notions of (special) neutrosophic $\mathcal{N}$ -UP-subalgebras, (special) neutrosophic $\mathcal{N}$ -near UP-filters, (special) neutrosophic $\mathcal{N}$ -UP-filters, (special) neutrosophic $\mathcal{N}$ -UP-ideals, and (special) neutrosophic $\mathcal{N}$ -strongly UP-ideals of UP-algebras are introduced, and several properties are investigated. Conditions for neutrosophic $\mathcal{N}$ -structures to be (special) neutrosophic $\mathcal{N}$ -UP-subalgebras, (special) neutrosophic $\mathcal{N}$ -near UP-filters, (special) neutrosophic $\mathcal{N}$ -UP-filters, (special) neutrosophic $\mathcal{N}$ -UP-ideals, and (special) neutrosophic $\mathcal{N}$ -strongly UP-ideals of UP-algebras are provided. Relations between (special) neutrosophic $\mathcal{N}$ -UP-subalgebras (resp., (special) neutrosophic $\mathcal{N}$ -near UP-filters, (special) neutrosophic $\mathcal{N}$ -UP-filters, (special) neutrosophic $\mathcal{N}$ -UP-ideals, (special) neutrosophic $\mathcal{N}$ -strongly UP-ideals) and their level subsets are considered.

Keywords: UP-algebra; (special) neutrosophic $\mathcal{N}$ -UP-subalgebra; (special) neutrosophic $\mathcal{N}$ -near UP-filter; (special) neutrosophic $\mathcal{N}$ -UP-filter; (special) neutrosophic $\mathcal{N}$ -UP-ideal; (special) neutrosophic $\mathcal{N}$ -strongly UP-ideal

1. Introduction

Among many algebraic structures, algebras of logic form important class of algebras. Examples of these are BCK-algebras [14], BCI-algebras [15], BCH-algebras [11], KU-algebras [28], SU-algebras [21] and others. They are strongly connected with logic. For example, BCI-algebras were introduced by Iséki [15] in 1966 have connections with BCI-logic being the BCI-system in combinatory logic which has application in the language of functional programming. BCK and BCI-algebras are two classes of logical algebras. They were introduced by Imai and Iséki [14, 15] in 1966 and have been extensively investigated by many researchers. It is known that the class of BCK-algebras is a proper subclass of the class of BCI-algebras.

The branch of the logical algebra, UP-algebras was introduced by Iampan [12] in 2017, and it is known that the class of KU-algebras [28] is a proper subclass of the class of UP-algebras. It have been examined by several researchers, for example, Somjanta et al. [32] introduced the notion of fuzzy sets in UP-algebras, the notion of intuitionistic fuzzy sets in UP-algebras was introduced by Kesorn et al. [22], Kaijæ et al. [20] introduced the notions of anti-fuzzy UP-ideals and anti-fuzzy UP-subalgebras of UP-algebras, the notion of Q -fuzzy sets in UP-algebras was introduced by Tanamoon et al. [37], etc.

Neutrosophy provides a foundation for a whole family of new mathematical theories with the generalization of both classical and fuzzy counterparts. In a neutrosophic set, an element has three associated defining functions such as truth membership function (T), indeterminate membership

function (I) and false membership function (F) defined on a universe of discourse X . These three functions are independent completely. The concept of neutrosophic logics was first introduced by Smarandache [31] in 1999. Jun et al. [16] introduced a new function, called a negative-valued function, and constructed $\mathcal{N}$ -structures in 2009. Khan et al. [23] discussed neutrosophic $\mathcal{N}$ -structures and their applications in semigroups in 2017. Jun et al. [17, 33] considered neutrosophic $\mathcal{N}$ -structures applied to BCK/BCI-algebras and neutrosophic commutative $\mathcal{N}$ -ideals in BCK-algebras in 2017. Jun et al. [19] studied neutrosophic positive implicative $\mathcal{N}$ -ideals in BCK-algebras in 2018. Abdel-Baset and his colleagues applied the notion of neutrosophic set theory in the new fields (see [1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 27]). Jun and his colleagues applied the notion of neutrosophic set theory in BCK/BCI-algebras (see [8, 18, 24, 26, 35, 36]).

The remaining part of the paper is structured as follows: Section 2 gives some definitions and properties of UP-algebras. Section 3 introduces the notions of neutrosophic $\mathcal{N}$ -UP-subalgebras, neutrosophic $\mathcal{N}$ -near UP-filters, neutrosophic $\mathcal{N}$ -UP-filters, neutrosophic $\mathcal{N}$ -UP-ideals, and neutrosophic $\mathcal{N}$ -strongly UP-ideals of UP-algebras, and a level subset of a neutrosophic $\mathcal{N}$ -structure is proved in Section 4. Section 5 introduces the notions of special neutrosophic $\mathcal{N}$ -UP-subalgebras, special neutrosophic $\mathcal{N}$ -near UP-filters, special neutrosophic $\mathcal{N}$ -UP-filters, special neutrosophic $\mathcal{N}$ -UP-ideals, and special neutrosophic $\mathcal{N}$ -strongly UP-ideals of UP-algebras, and a level subset of a neutrosophic $\mathcal{N}$ -structure of special type is proved in Section 6. This paper has been finalized with that result.

2. Basic results on UP-algebras

Before we begin our study, we will give the definition of a UP-algebra.

Definition 2.1 [12] An algebra $X = (X, \cdot, 0)$ of type $(2, 0)$ is called a UP-algebra where X is a nonempty set, $\cdot$ is a binary operation on X , and 0 is a fixed element of X (i.e., a nullary operation) if it satisfies the following axioms:

- (UP-1) $(\forall x, y, z \in X)((y \cdot z) \cdot ((x \cdot y) \cdot (x \cdot z)) = 0)$,
- (UP-2) $(\forall x \in X)(0 \cdot x = x)$,
- (UP-3) $(\forall x \in X)(x \cdot 0 = 0)$, and
- (UP-4) $(\forall x, y \in X)(x \cdot y = 0, y \cdot x = 0 \Rightarrow x = y)$.

From [12], we know that the notion of UP-algebras is a generalization of KU-algebras (see [28]).

Example 2.2 [30] Let X be a universal set and let $\Omega \in \mathcal{P}(X)$ where $\mathcal{P}(X)$ means the power set of X . Let $\mathcal{P}_\Omega(X) = \{A \in \mathcal{P}(X) \mid \Omega \subseteq A\}$. Define a binary operation $\cdot$ on $\mathcal{P}_\Omega(X)$ by putting $A \cdot B = B \cap (A^c \cup \Omega)$ for all $A, B \in \mathcal{P}_\Omega(X)$ where A^c means the complement of a subset A . Then $(\mathcal{P}_\Omega(X), \cdot, \Omega)$ is a UP-algebra and we shall call it the generalized power UP-algebra of type 1 with respect to Ω . Let $\mathcal{P}^\Omega(X) = \{A \in \mathcal{P}(X) \mid A \subseteq \Omega\}$. Define a binary operation $*$ on $\mathcal{P}^\Omega(X)$ by putting $A * B = B \cup (A^c \cap \Omega)$ for all $A, B \in \mathcal{P}^\Omega(X)$. Then $(\mathcal{P}^\Omega(X), *, \Omega)$ is a UP-algebra and we shall call it the generalized power UP-algebra of type 2 with respect to Ω . In particular, $(\mathcal{P}(X), \cdot, \emptyset)$ is a UP-algebra and we shall call it the power UP-algebra of type 1, and $(\mathcal{P}(X), *, X)$ is a UP-algebra and we shall call it the power UP-algebra of type 2.

Example 2.3 [9] Let $\mathbf{N}$ be the set of all natural numbers with two binary operations $\circ$ and $\bullet$ defined by

$$(\forall x, y \in \mathbf{N}) \left(x \circ y = \begin{cases} y & \text{if } x < y, \\ 0 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \right) \text{ and } (\forall x, y \in \mathbf{N}) \left(x \bullet y = \begin{cases} y & \text{if } x > y \text{ or } x = 0, \\ 0 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \right).$$

Then $(\mathbf{N}, \circ, 0)$ and $(\mathbf{N}, \bullet, 0)$ are UP-algebras.

Example 2.4 [25] Let $X = \{0,1,2,3,4,5\}$ be a set with a binary operation $\cdot$ defined by the following Cayley table:

$\cdot$	0	1	2	3	4	5
0	0	1	2	3	4	5
1	0	0	2	3	2	5
2	0	1	0	3	1	5
3	0	1	2	0	4	5
4	0	0	0	3	0	5
5	0	0	2	0	2	0

Then $(X, \cdot, 0)$ is a UP-algebra.

For more examples of UP-algebras, see [7, 13, 29, 30].

The following proposition is very important for the study of UP-algebras.

Proposition 2.5 [12, 13] In a UP-algebra $X = (X, \cdot, 0)$, the following properties hold:

1. $(\forall x \in X)(x \cdot x = 0)$,
2. $(\forall x, y, z \in X)(x \cdot y = 0, y \cdot z = 0 \Rightarrow x \cdot z = 0)$,
3. $(\forall x, y, z \in X)(x \cdot y = 0 \Rightarrow (z \cdot x) \cdot (z \cdot y) = 0)$,
4. $(\forall x, y, z \in X)(x \cdot y = 0 \Rightarrow (y \cdot z) \cdot (x \cdot z) = 0)$,
5. $(\forall x, y \in X)(x \cdot (y \cdot x) = 0)$,
6. $(\forall x, y \in X)((y \cdot x) \cdot x = 0 \Leftrightarrow x = y \cdot x)$,
7. $(\forall x, y \in X)(x \cdot (y \cdot y) = 0)$,
8. $(\forall a, x, y, z \in X)((x \cdot (y \cdot z)) \cdot (x \cdot ((a \cdot y) \cdot (a \cdot z))) = 0)$,
9. $(\forall a, x, y, z \in X)((((a \cdot x) \cdot (a \cdot y)) \cdot z) \cdot ((x \cdot y) \cdot z) = 0)$,
10. $(\forall x, y, z \in X)((x \cdot y) \cdot z \cdot (y \cdot z) = 0)$,
11. $(\forall x, y, z \in X)(x \cdot y = 0 \Rightarrow x \cdot (z \cdot y) = 0)$,
12. $(\forall x, y, z \in X)((x \cdot y) \cdot z \cdot (x \cdot (y \cdot z)) = 0)$, and
13. $(\forall a, x, y, z \in X)((x \cdot y) \cdot z \cdot (y \cdot (a \cdot z)) = 0)$.

On a UP-algebra $X = (X, \cdot, 0)$, we define a binary relation $\leq$ on X [12] as follows:

$$(\forall x, y \in X)(x \leq y \Leftrightarrow x \cdot y = 0).$$

Definition 2.6 [10, 12, 32] A nonempty subset S of a UP-algebra $(X, \cdot, 0)$ is called

1. a UP-subalgebra of X if $(\forall x, y \in S)(x \cdot y \in S)$.
2. a near UP-filter of X if
 - (a) the constant 0 of X is in S , and
 - (b) $(\forall x, y \in X)(y \in S \Rightarrow x \cdot y \in S)$.
3. a UP-filter of X if
 - (a) the constant 0 of X is in S , and
 - (b) $(\forall x, y \in X)(x \cdot y \in S, x \in S \Rightarrow y \in S)$.
4. a UP-ideal of X if
 - (a) the constant 0 of X is in S , and
 - (b) $(\forall x, y, z \in X)(x \cdot (y \cdot z) \in S, y \in S \Rightarrow x \cdot z \in S)$.
5. a strongly UP-ideal of X if

- (a) the constant 0 of X is in S , and
- (b) $(\forall x, y, z \in X)((z \cdot y) \cdot (z \cdot x) \in S, y \in S \Rightarrow x \in S)$.

Guntasow et al. [10] proved that the notion of UP-subalgebras is a generalization of near UP-filters, near UP-filters is a generalization of UP-filters, UP-filters is a generalization of UP-ideals, and UP-ideals is a generalization of strongly UP-ideals. Moreover, they also proved that a UP-algebra X is the only one strongly UP-ideal of itself.

Theorem 2.7 Let $\mathcal{N}$ be a nonempty family of near UP-filters of a UP-algebra $X = (X, \cdot, 0)$. Then $\cap \mathcal{N}$ and $\cup \mathcal{N}$ are near UP-filters of X .

Proof. Clearly, $0 \in N$ for all $N \in \mathcal{N}$. Then $0 \in \cap \mathcal{N}$. Let $x \in X$ and $y \in \cap \mathcal{N}$. Then $y \in N$ for all $N \in \mathcal{N}$. Since N is a near UP-filter of X , we have $x \cdot y \in N$ for all $N \in \mathcal{N}$ and so $x \cdot y \in \cap \mathcal{N}$. Hence, $\cap \mathcal{N}$ is a near UP-filter of X . Since $\cap \mathcal{N} \subseteq \cup \mathcal{N}$, we have $0 \in \cup \mathcal{N}$. Let $x \in X$ and $y \in \cup \mathcal{N}$. Then $y \in N$ for some $N \in \mathcal{N}$. Since N is a near UP-filter of X , we have $x \cdot y \in N \subseteq \cup \mathcal{N}$. Hence, $\cup \mathcal{N}$ is a near UP-filter of X .

3. Neutrosophic $\mathcal{N}$ -structures

We denote the family of all functions from a nonempty set X to the closed interval $[-1, 0]$ of the real line by $F(X, [-1, 0])$. An element of $F(X, [-1, 0])$ is called a *negative-valued function* from X to $[-1, 0]$ (briefly, $\mathcal{N}$ -function on X). An ordered pair (X, f) of X and an $\mathcal{N}$ -function f on X is called an $\mathcal{N}$ -structure.

A *neutrosophic $\mathcal{N}$ -structure* over a nonempty universe of discourse X [23] is defined to be the structure

$$X_N = \{(x, T_N(x), I_N(x), F_N(x)) \mid x \in X\}$$

where T_N, I_N and F_N are $\mathcal{N}$ -functions on X which are called the *negative truth membership function*, the *negative indeterminacy membership function* and the *negative falsity membership function* on X , respectively.

For the sake of simplicity, we will use the notation X_N or $X_N = (X, T_N, I_N, F_N)$ instead of the neutrosophic $\mathcal{N}$ -structure [16].

Definition 3.1 Let X_N be a neutrosophic $\mathcal{N}$ -structure over a nonempty set X . The neutrosophic $\mathcal{N}$ -structure $\bar{X}_N = (X, \bar{T}_N, \bar{I}_N, \bar{F}_N)$ defined by

$$(\forall x \in X) \begin{pmatrix} \bar{T}_N(x) & = -1 - T_N(x) \\ \bar{I}_N(x) & = -1 - I_N(x) \\ \bar{F}_N(x) & = -1 - F_N(x) \end{pmatrix} \tag{3.1}$$

is called the *complement* of X_N in X .

Remark 3.2 For all neutrosophic $\mathcal{N}$ -structure X_N over a nonempty set X , we have $X_N = \bar{\bar{X}}_N$.

Lemma 3.3 [33] Let f be an $\mathcal{N}$ -function on a nonempty set X . Then the following statements hold:

1. $(\forall x, y \in X)(-1 - \max\{f(x), f(y)\} = \min\{-1 - f(x), -1 - f(y)\})$, and

$$2. (\forall x, y \in X)(-1 - \min\{f(x), f(y)\} = \max\{-1 - f(x), -1 - f(y)\}).$$

The following lemmas are easily proved

Lemma 3.4 Let f be an $\mathcal{N}$ -function on a nonempty set X . Then the following statements hold:

1. $(\forall x, y, z \in X)(\bar{f}(x) \geq \min\{\bar{f}(y), \bar{f}(z)\} \Leftrightarrow f(x) \leq \max\{f(y), f(z)\}),$
2. $(\forall x, y, z \in X)(\bar{f}(x) \leq \min\{\bar{f}(y), \bar{f}(z)\} \Leftrightarrow f(x) \geq \max\{f(y), f(z)\}),$
3. $(\forall x, y, z \in X)(\bar{f}(x) \geq \max\{\bar{f}(y), \bar{f}(z)\} \Leftrightarrow f(x) \leq \min\{f(y), f(z)\}),$ and
4. $(\forall x, y, z \in X)(\bar{f}(x) \leq \max\{\bar{f}(y), \bar{f}(z)\} \Leftrightarrow f(x) \geq \min\{f(y), f(z)\}).$

In what follows, let X denote a UP-algebra $(X, \cdot, 0)$ unless otherwise specified.

Now, we introduce the notions of neutrosophic $\mathcal{N}$ -UP-subalgebras, neutrosophic $\mathcal{N}$ -near UP-filters, neutrosophic $\mathcal{N}$ -UP-filters, neutrosophic $\mathcal{N}$ -UP-ideals, and neutrosophic $\mathcal{N}$ -strongly UP-ideals of UP-algebras, provide the necessary examples, investigate their properties, and prove their generalizations.

Definition 3.5 A neutrosophic $\mathcal{N}$ -structure X_N over X is called a *neutrosophic $\mathcal{N}$ -UP-subalgebra* of X if it satisfies the following conditions:

$$(\forall x, y \in X)(T_N(x \cdot y) \leq \max\{T_N(x), T_N(y)\}), \tag{3.2}$$

$$(\forall x, y \in X)(I_N(x \cdot y) \geq \min\{I_N(x), I_N(y)\}), \tag{3.3}$$

$$(\forall x, y \in X)(F_N(x \cdot y) \leq \max\{F_N(x), F_N(y)\}). \tag{3.4}$$

Example 3.6 Let $X = \{0,1,2,3,4\}$ be a set with a binary operation $\cdot$ defined by the following Cayley table:

$\cdot$	0	1	2	3	4
0	0	1	2	3	4
1	0	0	2	3	4
2	0	0	0	3	4
3	0	0	2	0	4
4	0	0	0	0	0

Then $(X, \cdot, 0)$ is a UP-algebra. We define a neutrosophic $\mathcal{N}$ -structure X_N over X as follows:

$$T_N(0) = -0.8, I_N(0) = -0.3, F_N(0) = -0.8,$$

$$T_N(1) = -0.6, I_N(1) = -0.7, F_N(1) = -0.8,$$

$$T_N(2) = -0.4, I_N(2) = -0.8, F_N(2) = -0.7,$$

$$T_N(3) = -0.1, I_N(3) = -0.5, F_N(3) = -0.5,$$

$$T_N(4) = -0.2, I_N(4) = -0.9, F_N(4) = -0.3.$$

Hence, X_N is a neutrosophic $\mathcal{N}$ -UP-subalgebra of X .

Definition 3.7 A neutrosophic $\mathcal{N}$ -structure X_N over X is called a *neutrosophic $\mathcal{N}$ -near UP-filter* of X if it satisfies the following conditions:

$$(\forall x \in X)(T_N(0) \leq T_N(x)), \tag{3.5}$$

$$(\forall x \in X)(I_N(0) \geq I_N(x)), \tag{3.6}$$

$$(\forall x \in X)(F_N(0) \leq F_N(x)), \tag{3.7}$$

$$(\forall x, y \in X)(T_N(x \cdot y) \leq T_N(y)), \tag{3.8}$$

$$(\forall x, y \in X)(I_N(x \cdot y) \geq I_N(y)), \tag{3.9}$$

$$(\forall x, y \in X)(F_N(x \cdot y) \leq F_N(y)). \tag{3.10}$$

Example 3.8 Let $X = \{0,1,2,3,4\}$ be a set with a binary operation $\cdot$ defined by the following Cayley table:

$\cdot$	0	1	2	3	4
0	0	1	2	3	4
1	0	0	2	3	2
2	0	1	0	3	1
3	0	1	2	0	4
4	0	0	0	3	0

Then $(X, \cdot, 0)$ is a UP-algebra. We define a neutrosophic $\mathcal{N}$ -structure X_N over X as follows:

$$T_N(0) = -0.8, I_N(0) = -0.3, F_N(0) = -0.8,$$

$$T_N(1) = -0.6, I_N(1) = -0.7, F_N(1) = -0.6,$$

$$T_N(2) = -0.8, I_N(2) = -0.8, F_N(2) = -0.7,$$

$$T_N(3) = -0.1, I_N(3) = -0.5, F_N(3) = -0.5,$$

$$T_N(4) = -0.3, I_N(4) = -0.8, F_N(4) = -0.3.$$

Hence, X_N is a neutrosophic $\mathcal{N}$ -near UP-filter of X .

Definition 3.9 A neutrosophic $\mathcal{N}$ -structure X_N over X is called a *neutrosophic $\mathcal{N}$ -UP-filter* of X if it satisfies the following conditions: (3.5), (3.6), (3.7), and

$$(\forall x, y \in X)(T_N(y) \leq \max\{T_N(x \cdot y), T_N(x)\}), \tag{3.11}$$

$$(\forall x, y \in X)(I_N(y) \geq \min\{I_N(x \cdot y), I_N(x)\}), \tag{3.12}$$

$$(\forall x, y \in X)(F_N(y) \leq \max\{F_N(x \cdot y), F_N(x)\}). \tag{3.13}$$

Example 3.10 Let $X = \{0,1,2,3,4\}$ be a set with a binary operation $\cdot$ defined by the following Cayley table:

$\cdot$	0	1	2	3	4
0	0	1	2	3	4
1	0	0	2	0	0
2	0	1	0	0	4
3	0	1	2	0	4
4	0	1	2	3	0

Then $(X, \cdot, 0)$ is a UP-algebra. We define a neutrosophic $\mathcal{N}$ -structure X_N over X as follows:

$$T_N(0) = -0.9, I_N(0) = -0.2, F_N(0) = -0.8,$$

$$T_N(1) = -0.5, I_N(1) = -0.8, F_N(1) = -0.6,$$

$$T_N(2) = -0.2, I_N(2) = -0.6, F_N(2) = -0.3,$$

$$T_N(3) = -0.6, I_N(3) = -0.3, F_N(3) = -0.7,$$

$$T_N(4) = -0.7, I_N(4) = -0.3, F_N(4) = -0.8.$$

Hence, X_N is a neutrosophic $\mathcal{N}^c$ UP-filter of X .

Definition 3.11 A neutrosophic $\mathcal{N}^c$ -structure X_N over X is called a *neutrosophic $\mathcal{N}^c$ -UP-ideal* of X if it satisfies the following conditions: (3.5), (3.6), (3.7), and

$$(\forall x, y, z \in X)(T_N(x \cdot z) \leq \max\{T_N(x \cdot (y \cdot z)), T_N(y)\}), \tag{3.14}$$

$$(\forall x, y, z \in X)(I_N(x \cdot z) \geq \min\{I_N(x \cdot (y \cdot z)), I_N(y)\}), \tag{3.15}$$

$$(\forall x, y, z \in X)(F_N(x \cdot z) \leq \max\{F_N(x \cdot (y \cdot z)), F_N(y)\}). \tag{3.16}$$

Example 3.12 Let $X = \{0,1,2,3,4\}$ be a set with a binary operation $\cdot$ defined by the following Cayley table:

$\cdot$	0	1	2	3	4
0	0	1	2	3	4
1	0	0	2	3	4
2	0	1	0	3	4
3	0	0	2	0	4
4	0	1	2	3	0

Then $(X, \cdot, 0)$ is a UP-algebra. We define a neutrosophic $\mathcal{N}^c$ -structure X_N over X as follows:

$$T_N(0) = -0.8, I_N(0) = -0.3, F_N(0) = -0.8,$$

$$T_N(1) = -0.5, I_N(1) = -0.6, F_N(1) = -0.8,$$

$$T_N(2) = -0.4, I_N(2) = -0.8, F_N(2) = -0.7,$$

$$T_N(3) = -0.1, I_N(3) = -0.7, F_N(3) = -0.5,$$

$$T_N(4) = -0.2, I_N(4) = -0.8, F_N(4) = -0.3.$$

Hence, X_N is a neutrosophic $\mathcal{N}^c$ UP-ideal of X .

Definition 3.13 A neutrosophic $\mathcal{N}^c$ -structure X_N over X is called a *neutrosophic $\mathcal{N}^c$ -strongly UP-ideal* of X if it satisfies the following conditions: (3.5), (3.6), (3.7), and

$$(\forall x, y, z \in X)(T_N(x) \leq \max\{T_N((z \cdot y) \cdot (z \cdot x)), T_N(y)\}), \tag{3.17}$$

$$(\forall x, y, z \in X)(I_N(x) \geq \min\{I_N((z \cdot y) \cdot (z \cdot x)), I_N(y)\}), \tag{3.18}$$

$$(\forall x, y, z \in X)(F_N(x) \leq \max\{F_N((z \cdot y) \cdot (z \cdot x)), F_N(y)\}). \tag{3.19}$$

Example 3.14 Let $X = \{0,1,2,3,4\}$ be a set with a binary operation $\cdot$ defined by the following Cayley table:

$\cdot$	0	1	2	3	4
0	0	1	2	3	4
1	0	0	0	3	2
2	0	1	0	3	1
3	0	1	2	0	4
4	0	0	0	3	0

Then $(X, \cdot, 0)$ is a UP-algebra. We define a neutrosophic $\mathcal{N}^c$ -structure X_N over X as follows:

$$(\forall x \in X) \begin{pmatrix} T_N(x) = -1 \\ I_N(x) = -0.3 \\ F_N(x) = -0.7 \end{pmatrix}.$$

Hence, X_N is neutrosophic $\mathcal{N}^c$ -strongly UP-ideal of X .

Definition 3.15 A neutrosophic $\mathcal{N}^c$ -structure X_N over X is said to be *constant* if X_N is a constant function from X to $[-1, 0]^3$. That is, $T_N, I_N,$ and F_N are constant functions from X to $[-1, 0]$.

Theorem 3.16 Every neutrosophic $\mathcal{N}^c$ -UP-subalgebra of X satisfies the conditions (3.5), (3.6), and (3.7).

Proof. Assume that X_N is a neutrosophic $\mathcal{N}^c$ -UP-subalgebra of X . Then for all $x \in X$, by Proposition 2.5 (1), (3.2), (3.3), and (3.4), we have

$$\begin{aligned} T_N(0) &= T_N(x \cdot x) \leq \max\{T_N(x), T_N(x)\} = T_N(x), \\ I_N(0) &= I_N(x \cdot x) \geq \min\{I_N(x), I_N(x)\} = I_N(x), \\ F_N(0) &= F_N(x \cdot x) \leq \max\{F_N(x), F_N(x)\} = F_N(x). \end{aligned}$$

Hence, X_N satisfies the conditions (3.5), (3.6), and (3.7).

Theorem 3.17 A neutrosophic $\mathcal{N}^c$ -structure X_N over X is constant if and only if it is a neutrosophic $\mathcal{N}^c$ -strongly UP-ideal of X .

Proof. Assume that X_N is constant. Then for all $x \in X$, $T_N(x) = T_N(0), I_N(x) = I_N(0)$, and $F_N(x) = F_N(0)$ and so $T_N(0) \leq T_N(x), I_N(0) \geq I_N(x)$, and $F_N(0) \leq F_N(x)$. Next, for all $x, y, z \in X$,

$$\begin{aligned} T_N(x) &= T_N(0) = \max\{T_N(0), T_N(0)\} = \max\{T_N((z \cdot y) \cdot (z \cdot x)), T_N(y)\}, \\ I_N(x) &= I_N(0) = \min\{I_N(0), I_N(0)\} = \min\{I_N((z \cdot y) \cdot (z \cdot x)), I_N(y)\}, \\ F_N(x) &= F_N(0) = \max\{F_N(0), F_N(0)\} = \max\{F_N((z \cdot y) \cdot (z \cdot x)), F_N(y)\}. \end{aligned}$$

Hence, X_N is a neutrosophic $\mathcal{N}^c$ -strongly UP-ideal of X .

Conversely, assume that X_N is a neutrosophic $\mathcal{N}^c$ -strongly UP-ideal of X . For any $x \in X$, by Proposition 2.5 (1), (UP-2), (UP-3), (3.17), (3.18), and (3.19), we have

$$\begin{aligned} T_N(x) &\leq \max\{T_N((x \cdot 0) \cdot (x \cdot x)), T_N(0)\} = \max\{T_N(0 \cdot (x \cdot x)), T_N(0)\} = \max\{T_N(x \cdot x), T_N(0)\} \\ &= \max\{T_N(0), T_N(0)\} = T_N(0), \\ I_N(x) &\geq \min\{I_N((x \cdot 0) \cdot (x \cdot x)), I_N(0)\} = \min\{I_N(0 \cdot (x \cdot x)), I_N(0)\} = \min\{I_N(x \cdot x), I_N(0)\} \\ &= \min\{I_N(0), I_N(0)\} = I_N(0), \\ F_N(x) &\leq \max\{F_N((x \cdot 0) \cdot (x \cdot x)), F_N(0)\} = \max\{F_N(0 \cdot (x \cdot x)), F_N(0)\} = \max\{F_N(x \cdot x), F_N(0)\} \\ &= \max\{F_N(0), F_N(0)\} = F_N(0). \end{aligned}$$

Thus $T_N(x) = T_N(0), I_N(x) = I_N(0)$, and $F_N(x) = F_N(0)$ for all $x \in X$. Hence, X_N is constant.

Theorem 3.18 Every neutrosophic $\mathcal{N}^c$ -strongly UP-ideal of X is a neutrosophic $\mathcal{N}^c$ -UP-ideal.

Proof. Assume that X_N is a neutrosophic $\mathcal{N}^c$ -strong UP-ideal of X . Then X_N satisfies the conditions (3.5), (3.6), and (3.7). By Theorem 3.17, we have X_N is constant. Then for all $x \in X$, $T_N(x) = T_N(0), I_N(x) = I_N(0)$, and $F_N(x) = F_N(0)$. By Proposition 2.5 (5), (UP-3), (3.5), (3.6), (3.7), (3.17), (3.18), and (3.19), we have

$$\begin{aligned} T_N(x \cdot z) &= \max\{T_N((z \cdot y) \cdot (z \cdot (x \cdot z))), T_N(y)\} = \max\{T_N((z \cdot y) \cdot 0), T_N(y)\} = \max\{T_N(0), T_N(y)\} = T_N(y) \\ &\leq \max\{T_N(x \cdot (y \cdot z)), T_N(y)\}, \\ I_N(x \cdot z) &= \min\{I_N((z \cdot y) \cdot (z \cdot (x \cdot z))), I_N(y)\} = \min\{I_N((z \cdot y) \cdot 0), I_N(y)\} = \min\{I_N(0), I_N(y)\} = I_N(y) \\ &\geq \min\{I_N(x \cdot (y \cdot z)), I_N(y)\}, \\ F_N(x \cdot z) &= \max\{F_N((z \cdot y) \cdot (z \cdot (x \cdot z))), F_N(y)\} = \max\{F_N((z \cdot y) \cdot 0), F_N(y)\} = \max\{F_N(0), F_N(y)\} = F_N(y) \\ &\leq \max\{F_N(x \cdot (y \cdot z)), F_N(y)\}. \end{aligned}$$

Hence, X_N is a neutrosophic $\mathcal{N}$ -UP-ideal of X .

The following example show that the converse of Theorem 3.18 is not true.

Example 3.19 Let $X = \{0,1,2,3\}$ be a set with a binary operation $\cdot$ defined by the following Cayley table:

$\cdot$	0	1	2	3
0	0	1	2	3
1	0	0	2	3
2	0	1	0	3
3	0	1	2	0

Then $(X, \cdot, 0)$ is a UP-algebra. We define a neutrosophic $\mathcal{N}$ -structure X_N over X as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} T_N(0) &= -0.6, I_N(0) = -0.1, F_N(0) = -0.7, \\ T_N(1) &= -0.4, I_N(1) = -0.5, F_N(1) = -0.5, \\ T_N(2) &= -0.3, I_N(2) = -0.4, F_N(2) = -0.4, \\ T_N(3) &= -0.2, I_N(3) = -0.4, F_N(3) = -0.3. \end{aligned}$$

Hence, X_N is a neutrosophic $\mathcal{N}$ -UP-ideal of X . Since X_N is not constant, it follows from Theorem 3.17 that it is not a neutrosophic $\mathcal{N}$ -strongly UP-ideal of X .

Theorem 3.20 Every neutrosophic $\mathcal{N}$ -UP-ideal of X is a neutrosophic $\mathcal{N}$ -UP-filter.

Proof. Assume that X_N is a neutrosophic $\mathcal{N}$ -UP-ideal of X . Then X_N satisfies the conditions (3.5), (3.6), and (3.7). Next, let $x, y \in X$. By (UP-2), (3.14), (3.15), and (3.16), we have

$$\begin{aligned} T_N(y) &= T_N(0 \cdot y) \leq \max\{T_N(0 \cdot (x \cdot y)), T_N(x)\} = \max\{T_N(x \cdot y), T_N(x)\}, \\ I_N(y) &= I_N(0 \cdot y) \geq \min\{I_N(0 \cdot (x \cdot y)), I_N(x)\} = \min\{I_N(x \cdot y), I_N(x)\}, \\ F_N(y) &= F_N(0 \cdot y) \leq \max\{F_N(0 \cdot (x \cdot y)), F_N(x)\} = \max\{F_N(x \cdot y), F_N(x)\}. \end{aligned}$$

Hence, X_N is a neutrosophic $\mathcal{N}$ -UP-filter of X .

The following example show that the converse of Theorem 3.20 is not true.

Example 3.21 Let $X = \{0,1,2,3\}$ be a set with a binary operation $\cdot$ defined by the following Cayley table:

$\cdot$	0	1	2	3
0	0	1	2	3
1	0	0	2	2
2	0	1	0	2
3	0	1	0	0

Then $(X, \cdot, 0)$ is a UP-algebra. We define a neutrosophic $\mathcal{N}$ -structure X_N over X as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} T_N(0) &= -0.7, I_N(0) = -0.1, F_N(0) = -0.9, \\ T_N(1) &= -0.6, I_N(1) = -0.5, F_N(1) = -0.8, \\ T_N(2) &= -0.3, I_N(2) = -0.4, F_N(2) = -0.5, \\ T_N(3) &= -0.3, I_N(3) = -0.4, F_N(3) = -0.5. \end{aligned}$$

Hence, X_N is a neutrosophic $\mathcal{N}$ -UP-filter of X . Since $F_N(2 \cdot 3) = -0.3 > -0.8 = \max\{F_N(2 \cdot (1 \cdot 3)), F_N(1)\}$, we have X_N is not a neutrosophic $\mathcal{N}$ -UP-ideal of X .

Theorem 3.22 Every neutrosophic $\mathcal{N}$ -UP-filter of X is a neutrosophic $\mathcal{N}$ -near UP-filter.

Proof. Assume that X_N is a neutrosophic $\mathcal{N}^c$ UP-filter. Then X_N satisfies the conditions (3.5), (3.6), and (3.7). Next, let $x, y \in X$. By Proposition 2.5 (5), (3.5), (3.6), (3.7), (3.11), (3.12), and (3.13), we have

$$\begin{aligned} T_N(x \cdot y) &\leq \max\{T_N(y \cdot (x \cdot y)), T_N(y)\} = \max\{T_N(0), T_N(y)\} = T_N(y), \\ I_N(x \cdot y) &\geq \min\{I_N(y \cdot (x \cdot y)), I_N(y)\} = \min\{I_N(0), I_N(y)\} = I_N(y), \\ F_N(x \cdot y) &\leq \max\{F_N(y \cdot (x \cdot y)), F_N(y)\} = \max\{F_N(0), F_N(y)\} = F_N(y). \end{aligned}$$

Hence, X_N is a neutrosophic $\mathcal{N}^c$ -near UP-filter of X .

The following example show that the converse of Theorem 3.22 is not true.

Example 3.23 Let $X = \{0,1,2,3\}$ be a set with a binary operation $\cdot$ defined by the following Cayley table:

$\cdot$	0	1	2	3
0	0	1	2	3
1	0	0	1	3
2	0	0	0	3
3	0	1	1	0

Then $(X, \cdot, 0)$ is a UP-algebra. We define a neutrosophic $\mathcal{N}^c$ -structure X_N over X as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} T_N(0) &= -0.9, \quad I_N(0) = -0.3, \quad F_N(0) = -0.8, \\ T_N(1) &= -0.5, \quad I_N(1) = -0.7, \quad F_N(1) = -0.7, \\ T_N(2) &= -0.2, \quad I_N(2) = -0.8, \quad F_N(2) = -0.6, \\ T_N(3) &= -0.1, \quad I_N(3) = -0.5, \quad F_N(3) = -0.3. \end{aligned}$$

Hence, X_N is a neutrosophic $\mathcal{N}^c$ -near UP-filter of X . Since $I_N(2) = -0.8 < -0.7 = \min\{I_N(1 \cdot 2), I_N(1)\}$, we have X_N is not a neutrosophic $\mathcal{N}^c$ UP-filter of X .

Theorem 3.24 Every neutrosophic $\mathcal{N}^c$ -near UP-filter of X is a neutrosophic $\mathcal{N}^c$ UP-subalgebra.

Proof. Assume that X_N is a neutrosophic $\mathcal{N}^c$ -near UP-filter of X . Then for all $x, y \in X$, by (3.8), (3.9), and (3.10), we have

$$\begin{aligned} T_N(x \cdot y) &\leq T_N(y) \leq \max\{T_N(x), T_N(y)\}, \\ I_N(x \cdot y) &\geq I_N(y) \geq \min\{I_N(x), I_N(y)\}, \\ F_N(x \cdot y) &\leq F_N(y) \leq \max\{F_N(x), F_N(y)\}. \end{aligned}$$

Hence, X_N is a neutrosophic $\mathcal{N}^c$ UP-subalgebra of X .

The following example show that the converse of Theorem 3.24 is not true.

Example 3.25 Let $X = \{0,1,2,3\}$ be a set with a binary operation $\cdot$ defined by the following Cayley table:

$\cdot$	0	1	2	3
0	0	1	2	3
1	0	0	1	2
2	0	0	0	2
3	0	0	0	0

Then $(X, \cdot, 0)$ is a UP-algebra. We define a neutrosophic $\mathcal{N}^c$ -structure X_N over X as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} T_N(0) &= -0.8, \quad I_N(0) = -0.3, \quad F_N(0) = -0.8, \\ T_N(1) &= -0.6, \quad I_N(1) = -0.6, \quad F_N(1) = -0.8, \\ T_N(2) &= -0.4, \quad I_N(2) = -0.5, \quad F_N(2) = -0.7, \end{aligned}$$

$$T_N(3) = -0.1, I_N(3) = -0.7, F_N(3) = -0.5.$$

Hence, X_N is a neutrosophic $\mathcal{N}$ -UP-subalgebra of X . Since $I_N(1 \cdot 2) = -0.6 < -0.5 = I_N(2)$, we have X_N is not a neutrosophic $\mathcal{N}$ -near UP-filter of X .

By Theorems 3.18, 3.20, 3.22, and 3.24 and Examples 3.19, 3.21, 3.23, and 3.25, we have that the notion of neutrosophic $\mathcal{N}$ -UP-subalgebras is a generalization of neutrosophic $\mathcal{N}$ -near UP-filters, neutrosophic $\mathcal{N}$ -near UP-filters is a generalization of neutrosophic $\mathcal{N}$ -UP-filters, neutrosophic $\mathcal{N}$ -UP-filters is a generalization of neutrosophic $\mathcal{N}$ -UP-ideals, and neutrosophic $\mathcal{N}$ -UP-ideals is a generalization of neutrosophic $\mathcal{N}$ -strongly UP-ideals. Moreover, by Theorem 3.17, we obtain that neutrosophic $\mathcal{N}$ -strongly UP-ideals and constant neutrosophic $\mathcal{N}$ -structures coincide.

Theorem 3.26 If X_N is a neutrosophic $\mathcal{N}$ -UP-subalgebra of X satisfying the following condition:

$$(\forall x, y \in X) \left(x \cdot y \neq 0 \Rightarrow \begin{cases} T_N(x) \leq T_N(y) \\ I_N(x) \geq I_N(y) \\ F_N(x) \leq F_N(y) \end{cases} \right), \tag{3.20}$$

then X_N is a neutrosophic $\mathcal{N}$ -near UP-filter of X .

Proof. Assume that X_N is a neutrosophic $\mathcal{N}$ -UP-subalgebra of X satisfying the condition (3.20). By Theorem 3.16, we have X_N satisfies the conditions (3.5), (3.6), and (3.7). Next, let $x, y \in X$.

Case 1: $x \cdot y = 0$. Then, by (3.5), (3.6), and (3.7), we have

$$T_N(x \cdot y) = T_N(0) \leq T_N(y), I_N(x \cdot y) = I_N(0) \geq I_N(y), F_N(x \cdot y) = F_N(0) \leq F_N(y).$$

Case 2: $x \cdot y \neq 0$. Then, by (3.2), (3.3), (3.4), and (3.20), we have

$$T_N(x \cdot y) \leq \max\{T_N(x), T_N(y)\} = T_N(y), I_N(x \cdot y) \geq \min\{I_N(x), I_N(y)\} = I_N(y), \\ F_N(x \cdot y) \leq \max\{F_N(x), F_N(y)\} = F_N(y).$$

Hence, X_N is a neutrosophic $\mathcal{N}$ -near UP-filter of X .

Theorem 3.27 If X_N is a neutrosophic $\mathcal{N}$ -near UP-filter of X satisfying the following condition:

$$T_N = I_N = F_N, \tag{3.21}$$

then X_N is a neutrosophic $\mathcal{N}$ -UP-filter of X .

Proof. Assume that X_N is a neutrosophic $\mathcal{N}$ -near UP-filter of X satisfying the condition (3.21). Then X_N satisfies the conditions (3.5), (3.6), and (3.7). Next, let $x, y \in X$. Then, by (3.8), (3.9), and (3.21), we have

$$\max\{T_N(x \cdot y), T_N(x)\} = \max\{I_N(x \cdot y), T_N(x)\} \geq \max\{I_N(y), T_N(x)\} = \max\{T_N(y), T_N(x)\} \geq T_N(y), \\ \min\{I_N(x \cdot y), I_N(x)\} = \min\{T_N(x \cdot y), I_N(x)\} \leq \min\{T_N(y), I_N(x)\} = \min\{I_N(y), I_N(x)\} \leq I_N(y), \\ \max\{F_N(x \cdot y), F_N(x)\} = \max\{I_N(x \cdot y), F_N(x)\} \geq \max\{I_N(y), F_N(x)\} = \max\{F_N(y), F_N(x)\} \geq F_N(y).$$

Hence, X_N is a neutrosophic $\mathcal{N}$ -UP-filter of X .

Theorem 3.28 If X_N is a neutrosophic $\mathcal{N}$ -UP-filter of X satisfying the following condition:

$$(\forall x, y, z \in X) \begin{pmatrix} T_N(y \cdot (x \cdot z)) = T_N(x \cdot (y \cdot z)) \\ I_N(y \cdot (x \cdot z)) = I_N(x \cdot (y \cdot z)) \\ F_N(y \cdot (x \cdot z)) = F_N(x \cdot (y \cdot z)) \end{pmatrix}, \tag{3.22}$$

then X_N is a neutrosophic $\mathcal{N}$ -UP-ideal of X .

Proof. Assume that X_N is a neutrosophic $\mathcal{N}$ -UP-filter of X satisfying the condition (3.22). Then X_N satisfies the conditions (3.5), (3.6), and (3.7). Next, let $x, y, z \in X$. Then, by (3.11), (3.12), (3.13), and (3.22), we have

$$\begin{aligned} T_N(x \cdot z) &\leq \max\{T_N(y \cdot (x \cdot z)), T_N(y)\} = \max\{T_N(x \cdot (y \cdot z)), T_N(y)\}, T_N \\ I_N(x \cdot z) &\geq \min\{I_N(y \cdot (x \cdot z)), I_N(y)\} = \min\{I_N(x \cdot (y \cdot z)), I_N(y)\}, I_N \\ F_N(x \cdot z) &\leq \max\{F_N(y \cdot (x \cdot z)), F_N(y)\} = \max\{F_N(x \cdot (y \cdot z)), F_N(y)\}. F_N \end{aligned}$$

Hence, X_N is a neutrosophic $\mathcal{N}$ -UP-ideal of X .

Theorem 3.29 If X_N is a neutrosophic $\mathcal{N}$ -structure over X satisfying the following condition:

$$(\forall x, y, z \in X) \left(z \leq x \cdot y \Rightarrow \begin{cases} T_N(z) \leq \max\{T_N(x), T_N(y)\} \\ I_N(z) \geq \min\{I_N(x), I_N(y)\} \\ F_N(z) \leq \max\{F_N(x), F_N(y)\} \end{cases} \right), \tag{3.23}$$

then X_N is a neutrosophic $\mathcal{N}$ -UP-subalgebra of X .

Proof. Assume that X_N is a neutrosophic $\mathcal{N}$ -structure over X satisfying the condition (3.23). Let $x, y \in X$. By Proposition 2.5 (1), we have $(x \cdot y) \cdot (x \cdot y) = 0$, that is, $x \cdot y \leq x \cdot y$. It follows from (3.23) that

$$T_N(x \cdot y) \leq \max\{T_N(x), T_N(y)\}, I_N(x \cdot y) \geq \min\{I_N(x), I_N(y)\}, F_N(x \cdot y) \leq \max\{F_N(x), F_N(y)\}.$$

Hence, X_N is a neutrosophic $\mathcal{N}$ -UP-subalgebra of X .

Theorem 3.30 If X_N is a neutrosophic $\mathcal{N}$ -structure over X satisfying the following condition:

$$(\forall x, y, z \in X) \left(z \leq x \cdot y \Rightarrow \begin{cases} T_N(z) \leq T_N(y) \\ I_N(z) \geq I_N(y) \\ F_N(z) \leq F_N(y) \end{cases} \right), \tag{3.24}$$

then X_N is a neutrosophic $\mathcal{N}$ -near UP-filter of X .

Proof. Assume that X_N is a neutrosophic $\mathcal{N}$ -structure over X satisfying the condition (3.24). Let $x \in X$. By (UP-2) and Proposition 2.5 (1), we have $0 \cdot (x \cdot x) = 0$, that is, $0 \leq x \cdot x$. It follows from (3.24) that $T_N(0) \leq T_N(x), I_N(0) \geq I_N(x)$, and $F_N(0) \leq F_N(x)$. Next, let $x, y \in X$. By Proposition 2.5 (1), we have $(x \cdot y) \cdot (x \cdot y) = 0$, that is, $x \cdot y \leq x \cdot y$. It follows from (3.24) that $T_N(x \cdot y) \leq T_N(y), I_N(x \cdot y) \geq I_N(y)$, and $F_N(x \cdot y) \leq F_N(y)$. Hence, X_N is a neutrosophic $\mathcal{N}$ -near UP-filter of X .

Theorem 3.31 If X_N is a neutrosophic $\mathcal{N}$ -structure over X satisfying the following condition:

$$(\forall x, y, z \in X) \left(z \leq x \cdot y \Rightarrow \begin{cases} T_N(y) \leq \max\{T_N(z), T_N(x)\} \\ I_N(y) \geq \min\{I_N(z), I_N(x)\} \\ F_N(y) \leq \max\{F_N(z), F_N(x)\} \end{cases} \right), \tag{3.25}$$

then X_N is a neutrosophic $\mathcal{N}$ -UP-filter of X .

Proof. Assume that X_N is a neutrosophic $\mathcal{N}$ -structure over X satisfying the condition (3.25). Let $x \in X$. By (UP-3), we have $x \cdot (x \cdot 0) = 0$, that is, $x \leq x \cdot 0$. It follows from (3.25) that

$$\begin{aligned} T_N(0) &\leq \max\{T_N(x), T_N(x)\} = T_N(x), I_N(0) \geq \min\{I_N(x), I_N(x)\} = I_N(x), \\ F_N(0) &\leq \max\{F_N(x), F_N(x)\} = F_N(x). \end{aligned}$$

Next, let $x, y \in X$. By Proposition 2.5 (1), we have $(x \cdot y) \cdot (x \cdot y) = 0$, that is, $x \cdot y \leq x \cdot y$. It follows from (3.25) that

$$T_N(y) \leq \max\{T_N(x \cdot y), T_N(x)\}, I_N(y) \geq \min\{I_N(x \cdot y), I_N(x)\}, F_N(y) \leq \max\{F_N(x \cdot y), F_N(x)\}.$$

Hence, X_N is a neutrosophic $\mathcal{N}$ -UP-filter of X .

Theorem 3.32 If X_N is a neutrosophic $\mathcal{N}$ -structure over X satisfying the following condition:

$$(\forall a, x, y, z \in X) \left(a \leq x \cdot (y \cdot z) \Rightarrow \begin{cases} T_N(x \cdot z) \leq \max\{T_N(a), T_N(y)\} \\ I_N(x \cdot z) \geq \min\{I_N(a), I_N(y)\} \\ F_N(x \cdot z) \leq \max\{F_N(a), F_N(y)\} \end{cases} \right), \tag{3.26}$$

then X_N is a neutrosophic $\mathcal{N}$ -UP-ideal of X .

Proof. Assume that X_N is a neutrosophic $\mathcal{N}$ -structure over X satisfying the condition (3.26). Let $x \in X$. By (UP-3), we have $x \cdot (0 \cdot (x \cdot 0)) = 0$, that is, $x \leq 0 \cdot (x \cdot 0)$. It follows from (3.26) and (UP-2) that

$$\begin{aligned} T_N(0) = T_N(0 \cdot 0) &\leq \max\{T_N(x), T_N(x)\} = T_N(x), I_N(0) = I_N(0 \cdot 0) \geq \min\{I_N(x), I_N(x)\} = I_N(x), \\ F_N(0) = F_N(0 \cdot 0) &\leq \max\{F_N(x), F_N(x)\} = F_N(x). \end{aligned}$$

Next, let $x, y, z \in X$. By Proposition 2.5 (1), we have $(x \cdot (y \cdot z)) \cdot (x \cdot (y \cdot z)) = 0$, that is, $x \cdot (y \cdot z) \leq x \cdot (y \cdot z)$. It follows from (3.26) that

$$\begin{aligned} T_N(x \cdot z) &\leq \max\{T_N(x \cdot (y \cdot z)), T_N(y)\}, I_N(x \cdot z) \geq \min\{I_N(x \cdot (y \cdot z)), I_N(y)\}, \\ F_N(x \cdot z) &\leq \max\{F_N(x \cdot (y \cdot z)), F_N(y)\}. \end{aligned}$$

Hence, X_N is a neutrosophic $\mathcal{N}$ -UP-ideal of X .

For any fixed numbers $\alpha^-, \alpha^+, \beta^-, \beta^+, \gamma^-, \gamma^+ \in [-1, 0]$ such that $\alpha^- < \alpha^+, \beta^- < \beta^+, \gamma^- < \gamma^+$ and a nonempty subset G of X , a neutrosophic $\mathcal{N}$ -structure $X_N^G[\alpha^-, \beta^+, \gamma^-] = (X, T_N^G[\alpha^-, \beta^+, \gamma^-], I_N^G[\alpha^-, \beta^+, \gamma^-], F_N^G[\alpha^-, \beta^+, \gamma^-])$ over X where $T_N^G[\alpha^-, \beta^+, \gamma^-]$, $I_N^G[\alpha^-, \beta^+, \gamma^-]$, and $F_N^G[\alpha^-, \beta^+, \gamma^-]$ are $\mathcal{N}$ -functions on X which are given as follows:

$$T_N^G[\alpha^-, \beta^+, \gamma^-](x) = \begin{cases} \alpha^- & \text{if } x \in G, \\ \alpha^+ & \text{otherwise,} \end{cases} I_N^G[\alpha^-, \beta^+, \gamma^-](x) = \begin{cases} \beta^+ & \text{if } x \in G, \\ \beta^- & \text{otherwise,} \end{cases} F_N^G[\alpha^-, \beta^+, \gamma^-](x) = \begin{cases} \gamma^- & \text{if } x \in G, \\ \gamma^+ & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases}$$

Lemma 3.33 If the constant 0 of X is in a nonempty subset G of X , then a neutrosophic $\mathcal{N}$ -structure $X_N^G[\alpha^-, \beta^+, \gamma^-]$ over X satisfies the conditions (3.5), (3.6), and (3.7).

Proof. If $0 \in G$, then $T_N^G[\alpha^-, \beta^+, \gamma^-](0) = \alpha^-, I_N^G[\alpha^-, \beta^+, \gamma^-](0) = \beta^+, F_N^G[\alpha^-, \beta^+, \gamma^-](0) = \gamma^-$. Thus

$$(\forall x \in X) \begin{pmatrix} T_N^G[\alpha^-, \beta^+, \gamma^-](0) = \alpha^- \leq T_N^G[\alpha^-, \beta^+, \gamma^-](x) \\ I_N^G[\alpha^-, \beta^+, \gamma^-](0) = \beta^+ \geq I_N^G[\alpha^-, \beta^+, \gamma^-](x) \\ F_N^G[\alpha^-, \beta^+, \gamma^-](0) = \gamma^- \leq F_N^G[\alpha^-, \beta^+, \gamma^-](x) \end{pmatrix}.$$

Hence, $X_N^G[\alpha^-, \beta^+, \gamma^-]$ satisfies the conditions (3.5), (3.6), and (3.7).

Lemma 3.34 If a neutrosophic $\mathcal{N}^c$ -structure $X_N^G[\alpha^-, \beta^+, \gamma^-]$ over X satisfies the condition (3.5) (resp., (3.6), (3.7)), then the constant 0 of X is in a nonempty subset G of X .

Proof. Assume that the neutrosophic $\mathcal{N}^c$ -structure $X_N^G[\alpha^-, \beta^+, \gamma^-]$ over X satisfies the condition (3.5).

Then $T_N^G[\alpha^+](0) \leq T_N^G[\alpha^+](x)$ for all $x \in X$. Since G is nonempty, there exists $g \in G$. Thus

$$T_N^G[\alpha^+](g) = \alpha^-, \text{ so } T_N^G[\alpha^+](0) \leq T_N^G[\alpha^+](g) = \alpha^- \leq T_N^G[\alpha^+](0), \text{ that is, } T_N^G[\alpha^+](0) = \alpha^-. \text{ Hence, } 0 \in G.$$

Theorem 3.35 A neutrosophic $\mathcal{N}^c$ -structure $X_N^G[\alpha^-, \beta^+, \gamma^-]$ over X is a neutrosophic $\mathcal{N}^c$ -UP-subalgebra of X if and only if a nonempty subset G of X is a UP-subalgebra of X .

Proof. Assume that $X_N^G[\alpha^-, \beta^+, \gamma^-]$ is a neutrosophic $\mathcal{N}^c$ -UP-subalgebra of X . Let $x, y \in G$. Then

$$T_N^G[\alpha^+](x) = \alpha^- = T_N^G[\alpha^+](y). \text{ Thus, by (3.2), we have}$$

$$T_N^G[\alpha^+](x \cdot y) \leq \max\{T_N^G[\alpha^+](x), T_N^G[\alpha^+](y)\} = \alpha^- \leq T_N^G[\alpha^+](x \cdot y)$$

and so $T_N^G[\alpha^+](x \cdot y) = \alpha^-$. Thus $x \cdot y \in G$. Hence, G is a UP-subalgebra of X .

Conversely, assume that G is a UP-subalgebra of X . Let $x, y \in X$.

Case 1: $x, y \in G$. Then

$$T_N^G[\alpha^+](x) = \alpha^- = T_N^G[\alpha^+](y), I_N^G[\beta^-](x) = \beta^+ = I_N^G[\beta^-](y), F_N^G[\gamma^-](x) = \gamma^- = F_N^G[\gamma^-](y).$$

Thus

$$\max\{T_N^G[\alpha^+](x), T_N^G[\alpha^+](y)\} = \alpha^-, \min\{I_N^G[\beta^-](x), I_N^G[\beta^-](y)\} = \beta^+, \max\{F_N^G[\gamma^-](x), F_N^G[\gamma^-](y)\} = \gamma^-.$$

Since G is a UP-subalgebra of X , we have $x \cdot y \in G$ and so $T_N^G[\alpha^+](x \cdot y) = \alpha^-$, $I_N^G[\beta^-](x \cdot y) = \beta^+$,

and $F_N^G[\gamma^-](x \cdot y) = \gamma^-$. Hence,

$$T_N^G[\alpha^+](x \cdot y) = \alpha^- \leq \alpha^- = \max\{T_N^G[\alpha^+](x), T_N^G[\alpha^+](y)\}, I_N^G[\beta^-](x \cdot y) = \beta^+ \geq \beta^+ = \min\{I_N^G[\beta^-](x), I_N^G[\beta^-](y)\},$$

$$F_N^G[\gamma^-](x \cdot y) = \gamma^- \leq \gamma^- = \max\{F_N^G[\gamma^-](x), F_N^G[\gamma^-](y)\}.$$

Case 2: $x \notin G$ or $y \notin G$. Then

$$T_N^G[\alpha^+](x) = \alpha^+ \text{ or } T_N^G[\alpha^+](y) = \alpha^+, I_N^G[\beta^-](x) = \beta^- \text{ or } I_N^G[\beta^-](y) = \beta^-, F_N^G[\gamma^-](x) = \gamma^+ \text{ or } F_N^G[\gamma^-](y) = \gamma^+.$$

Thus

$$\max\{T_N^G[\alpha^+](x), T_N^G[\alpha^+](y)\} = \alpha^+, \min\{I_N^G[\beta^-](x), I_N^G[\beta^-](y)\} = \beta^-, \max\{F_N^G[\gamma^-](x), F_N^G[\gamma^-](y)\} = \gamma^+.$$

Therefore,

$$T_N^G[\alpha^+](x \cdot y) \leq \alpha^+ = \max\{T_N^G[\alpha^+](x), T_N^G[\alpha^+](y)\}, \quad I_N^G[\beta^+](x \cdot y) \geq \beta^- = \min\{I_N^G[\beta^+](x), I_N^G[\beta^+](y)\},$$

$$F_N^G[\gamma^+](x \cdot y) \leq \gamma^+ = \max\{F_N^G[\gamma^+](x), F_N^G[\gamma^+](y)\}.$$

Hence, $X_N^G[\alpha^+, \beta^+, \gamma^+]$ is a neutrosophic $\mathcal{N}$ -UP-subalgebra of X .

Theorem 3.36 A neutrosophic $\mathcal{N}$ -structure $X_N^G[\alpha^+, \beta^+, \gamma^+]$ over X is a neutrosophic $\mathcal{N}$ -near UP-filter of X if and only if a nonempty subset G of X is a near UP-filter of X .

Proof. Assume that $X_N^G[\alpha^+, \beta^+, \gamma^+]$ is neutrosophic $\mathcal{N}$ -near UP-filter of X . Since $X_N^G[\alpha^+, \beta^+, \gamma^+]$ satisfies the condition (3.5), it follows from Lemma 3.34 that $0 \in G$. Next, let $x \in X$ and $y \in G$. Then $T_N^G[\alpha^+](y) = \alpha^+$. Thus, by (3.8), we have $T_N^G[\alpha^+](x \cdot y) \leq T_N^G[\alpha^+](y) = \alpha^+ \leq T_N^G[\alpha^+](x \cdot y)$ and so $T_N^G[\alpha^+](x \cdot y) = \alpha^+$. Thus $x \cdot y \in G$. Hence, G is a near UP-filter of X .

Conversely, assume that G is a near UP-filter of X . Since $0 \in G$, it follows from Lemma 3.33 that $X_N^G[\alpha^+, \beta^+, \gamma^+]$ satisfies the conditions (3.5), (3.6), and (3.7). Next, let $x, y \in X$.

Case 1: $y \in G$. Then $T_N^G[\alpha^+](y) = \alpha^+, I_N^G[\beta^+](y) = \beta^+$, and $F_N^G[\gamma^+](y) = \gamma^+$. Since G is a near UP-filter of X , we have $x \cdot y \in G$ and so $T_N^G[\alpha^+](x \cdot y) = \alpha^+, I_N^G[\beta^+](x \cdot y) = \beta^+$, and $F_N^G[\gamma^+](x \cdot y) = \gamma^+$. Thus

$$T_N^G[\alpha^+](x \cdot y) = \alpha^+ \leq \alpha^+ = T_N^G[\alpha^+](y), \quad I_N^G[\beta^+](x \cdot y) = \beta^+ \geq \beta^+ = I_N^G[\beta^+](y),$$

$$F_N^G[\gamma^+](x \cdot y) = \gamma^+ \leq \gamma^+ = F_N^G[\gamma^+](y).$$

Case 2: $y \notin G$. Then $T_N^G[\alpha^+](y) = \alpha^+, I_N^G[\beta^+](y) = \beta^+$, and $F_N^G[\gamma^+](y) = \gamma^+$. Thus

$$T_N^G[\alpha^+](x \cdot y) \leq \alpha^+ = T_N^G[\alpha^+](y), \quad I_N^G[\beta^+](x \cdot y) \geq \beta^+ = I_N^G[\beta^+](y), \quad F_N^G[\gamma^+](x \cdot y) \leq \gamma^+ = F_N^G[\gamma^+](y).$$

Hence, $X_N^G[\alpha^+, \beta^+, \gamma^+]$ is a neutrosophic $\mathcal{N}$ -near UP-filter of X .

Theorem 3.37 A neutrosophic $\mathcal{N}$ -structure $X_N^G[\alpha^+, \beta^+, \gamma^+]$ over X is a neutrosophic $\mathcal{N}$ -UP-filter of X if and only if a nonempty subset G of X is a UP-filter of X .

Proof. Assume that $X_N^G[\alpha^+, \beta^+, \gamma^+]$ is a neutrosophic $\mathcal{N}$ -UP-filter of X . Since $X_N^G[\alpha^+, \beta^+, \gamma^+]$ satisfies the condition (3.5), it follows from Lemma 3.34 that $0 \in G$. Next, let $x, y \in X$ be such that $x \cdot y \in G$ and $x \in G$. Then $T_N^G[\alpha^+](x \cdot y) = \alpha^+ = T_N^G[\alpha^+](x)$. Thus, by (3.11), we have

$$T_N^G[\alpha^-](y) \leq \max\{T_N^G[\alpha^-](x \cdot y), T_N^G[\alpha^-](x)\} = \alpha^- \leq T_N^G[\alpha^-](y)$$

and so $T_N^G[\alpha^-](y) = \alpha^-$. Thus $y \in G$. Hence, G is a UP-filter of X .

Conversely, assume that G is a UP-filter of X . Since $0 \in G$, it follows from Lemma 3.33 that $X_N^G[\alpha^-, \beta^+, \gamma^-]$ satisfies the conditions (3.5), (3.6), and (3.7). Next, let $x, y \in X$.

Case 1: $x \cdot y \in G$ and $x \in G$. Then

$$T_N^G[\alpha^-](x \cdot y) = \alpha^- = T_N^G[\alpha^-](x), \quad I_N^G[\beta^+](x \cdot y) = \beta^+ = I_N^G[\beta^+](x), \quad F_N^G[\gamma^-](x \cdot y) = \gamma^- = F_N^G[\gamma^-](x).$$

Since G is a UP-filter of X , we have $y \in G$ and so $T_N^G[\alpha^-](y) = \alpha^-$, $I_N^G[\beta^+](y) = \beta^+$, and

$F_N^G[\gamma^-](y) = \gamma^-$. Thus

$$T_N^G[\alpha^-](y) = \alpha^- \leq \alpha^- = \max\{T_N^G[\alpha^-](x \cdot y), T_N^G[\alpha^-](x)\}, \quad I_N^G[\beta^+](y) = \beta^+ \geq \beta^+ = \min\{I_N^G[\beta^+](x \cdot y), I_N^G[\beta^+](x)\},$$

$$F_N^G[\gamma^-](y) = \gamma^- \leq \gamma^- = \max\{F_N^G[\gamma^-](x \cdot y), F_N^G[\gamma^-](x)\}.$$

Case 2: $x \cdot y \notin G$ or $x \notin G$. Then

$$T_N^G[\alpha^-](x \cdot y) = \alpha^+ \text{ or } T_N^G[\alpha^-](x) = \alpha^+, \quad I_N^G[\beta^+](x \cdot y) = \beta^- \text{ or } I_N^G[\beta^+](x) = \beta^-,$$

$$F_N^G[\gamma^-](x \cdot y) = \gamma^+ \text{ or } F_N^G[\gamma^-](x) = \gamma^+.$$

Thus

$$\max\{T_N^G[\alpha^-](x \cdot y), T_N^G[\alpha^-](x)\} = \alpha^+, \quad \min\{I_N^G[\beta^+](x \cdot y), I_N^G[\beta^+](x)\} = \beta^-, \quad \max\{F_N^G[\gamma^-](x \cdot y), F_N^G[\gamma^-](x)\} = \gamma^+.$$

Therefore,

$$T_N^G[\alpha^-](y) \leq \alpha^+ = \max\{T_N^G[\alpha^-](x \cdot y), T_N^G[\alpha^-](x)\}, \quad I_N^G[\beta^+](y) \geq \beta^- = \min\{I_N^G[\beta^+](x \cdot y), I_N^G[\beta^+](x)\},$$

$$F_N^G[\gamma^-](y) \leq \gamma^+ = \max\{F_N^G[\gamma^-](x \cdot y), F_N^G[\gamma^-](x)\}.$$

Hence, $X_N^G[\alpha^-, \beta^+, \gamma^-]$ is a neutrosophic $\mathcal{N}^c$ -UP-filter of X .

Theorem 3.38 A neutrosophic $\mathcal{N}^c$ -structure $X_N^G[\alpha^-, \beta^+, \gamma^-]$ over X is a neutrosophic $\mathcal{N}^c$ -UP-ideal of X if and only if a nonempty subset G of X is a UP-ideal of X .

Proof. Assume that $X_N^G[\alpha^-, \beta^+, \gamma^-]$ is a neutrosophic $\mathcal{N}^c$ -UP-ideal of X . Since $X_N^G[\alpha^-, \beta^+, \gamma^-]$ satisfies the condition (3.5), it follows from Lemma 3.34 that $0 \in G$. Next, let $x, y, z \in X$ be such that $x \cdot (y \cdot z) \in G$ and $y \in G$. Then $T_N^G[\alpha^-](x \cdot (y \cdot z)) = \alpha^- = T_N^G[\alpha^-](y)$. Thus, by (3.17), we have

$$T_N^G[\alpha^+](x \cdot z) \leq \max\{T_N^G[\alpha^+](x \cdot (y \cdot z)), T_N^G[\alpha^+](y)\} = \alpha^- \leq T_N^G[\alpha^+](x \cdot z)$$

and so $T_N^G[\alpha^+](x \cdot z) = \alpha^-$. Thus $x \cdot z \in G$. Hence, G is a UP-ideal of X .

Conversely, assume that G is a UP-ideal of X . Since $0 \in G$, it follows from Lemma 3.33 that $X_N^G[\alpha^+, \beta^+, \gamma^-]$ satisfies the conditions (3.5), (3.6), and (3.7). Next, let $x, y, z \in X$.

Case 1: $x \cdot (y \cdot z) \in G$ and $y \in G$. Then

$$T_N^G[\alpha^+](x \cdot (y \cdot z)) = \alpha^- = T_N^G[\alpha^+](y), I_N^G[\beta^+](x \cdot (y \cdot z)) = \beta^+ = I_N^G[\beta^+](y), F_N^G[\gamma^-](x \cdot (y \cdot z)) = \gamma^- = F_N^G[\gamma^-](y).$$

Thus

$$\max\{T_N^G[\alpha^+](x \cdot (y \cdot z)), T_N^G[\alpha^+](y)\} = \alpha^-, \min\{I_N^G[\beta^+](x \cdot (y \cdot z)), I_N^G[\beta^+](y)\} = \beta^+,$$

$$\max\{F_N^G[\gamma^-](x \cdot (y \cdot z)), F_N^G[\gamma^-](y)\} = \gamma^-.$$

Since G is a UP-ideal of X , we have $x \cdot z \in G$ and so $T_N^G[\alpha^+](x \cdot z) = \alpha^-, I_N^G[\beta^+](x \cdot z) = \beta^+$, and

$F_N^G[\gamma^-](x \cdot z) = \gamma^-$. Thus

$$T_N^G[\alpha^+](x \cdot z) = \alpha^- \leq \alpha^- = \max\{T_N^G[\alpha^+](x \cdot (y \cdot z)), T_N^G[\alpha^+](y)\},$$

$$I_N^G[\beta^+](x \cdot z) = \beta^+ \geq \beta^+ = \min\{I_N^G[\beta^+](x \cdot (y \cdot z)), I_N^G[\beta^+](y)\},$$

$$F_N^G[\gamma^-](x \cdot z) = \gamma^- \leq \gamma^- = \max\{F_N^G[\gamma^-](x \cdot (y \cdot z)), F_N^G[\gamma^-](y)\}.$$

Case 2: $x \cdot (y \cdot z) \notin G$ or $y \notin G$. Then

$$T_N^G[\alpha^+](x \cdot (y \cdot z)) = \alpha^+ \text{ or } T_N^G[\alpha^+](y) = \alpha^+, I_N^G[\beta^+](x \cdot (y \cdot z)) = \beta^- \text{ or } I_N^G[\beta^+](y) = \beta^-,$$

$$F_N^G[\gamma^-](x \cdot (y \cdot z)) = \gamma^+ \text{ or } F_N^G[\gamma^-](y) = \gamma^+.$$

Thus

$$\max\{T_N^G[\alpha^+](x \cdot (y \cdot z)), T_N^G[\alpha^+](y)\} = \alpha^+, \min\{I_N^G[\beta^+](x \cdot (y \cdot z)), I_N^G[\beta^+](y)\} = \beta^-,$$

$$\max\{F_N^G[\gamma^-](x \cdot (y \cdot z)), F_N^G[\gamma^-](y)\} = \gamma^+.$$

Therefore,

$$T_N^G[\alpha^+](x \cdot z) \leq \alpha^+ = \max\{T_N^G[\alpha^+](x \cdot (y \cdot z)), T_N^G[\alpha^+](y)\},$$

$$I_N^G[\beta^+](x \cdot z) \geq \beta^- = \min\{I_N^G[\beta^+](x \cdot (y \cdot z)), I_N^G[\beta^+](y)\},$$

$$F_N^G[\gamma^-](x \cdot z) \leq \gamma^+ = \max\{F_N^G[\gamma^-](x \cdot (y \cdot z)), F_N^G[\gamma^-](y)\}.$$

Hence, $X_N^G[\alpha^-, \beta^+, \gamma^-]$ is a neutrosophic $\mathcal{N}$ -UP-ideal of X .

Theorem 3.39 A neutrosophic $\mathcal{N}$ -structure $X_N^G[\alpha^-, \beta^+, \gamma^-]$ over X is a neutrosophic $\mathcal{N}$ -strongly UP-ideal of X if and only if a nonempty subset G of X is a strongly UP-ideal of X .

Proof. Assume that $X_N^G[\alpha^-, \beta^+, \gamma^-]$ is a neutrosophic $\mathcal{N}$ -strongly UP-ideal of X . By Theorem 3.17, we have $X_N^G[\alpha^-, \beta^+, \gamma^-]$ is constant, that is, $T_N^G[\alpha^+]$ is constant. Since G is nonempty, we have $T_N^G[\alpha^+](x) = \alpha^-$ for all $x \in X$. Thus $G = X$. Hence, G is a strongly UP-ideal of X .

Conversely, assume that G is a strongly UP-ideal of X . Then $G = X$, so

$$(\forall x \in X) \begin{pmatrix} T_N^G[\alpha^+](x) = \alpha^- \\ I_N^G[\beta^-](x) = \beta^+ \\ F_N^G[\gamma^+](x) = \gamma^- \end{pmatrix}.$$

Thus $T_N^G[\alpha^+], I_N^G[\beta^-]$, and $F_N^G[\gamma^+]$ are constant, that is, $X_N^G[\alpha^-, \beta^+, \gamma^-]$ is constant. By Theorem 3.17, we have $X_N^G[\alpha^-, \beta^+, \gamma^-]$ is a neutrosophic $\mathcal{N}$ -strongly UP-ideal of X .

4. Level subsets of a neutrosophic $\mathcal{N}$ -structure

In this section, we discuss the relationships among neutrosophic $\mathcal{N}$ -UP-subalgebras (resp., neutrosophic $\mathcal{N}$ -near UP-filters, neutrosophic $\mathcal{N}$ -UP-filters, neutrosophic $\mathcal{N}$ -UP-ideals, neutrosophic $\mathcal{N}$ -strongly UP-ideals) of UP-algebras and their level subsets.

Definition 4.1 [34] Let f be an $\mathcal{N}$ -function on a nonempty set X . For any $t \in [-1, 0]$, the sets

$$U(f; t) = \{x \in X \mid f(x) \geq t\}, L(f; t) = \{x \in X \mid f(x) \leq t\}, E(f; t) = \{x \in X \mid f(x) = t\}$$

are called an upper t -level subset, a lower t -level subset, and an equal t -level subset of f , respectively.

Theorem 4.2 A neutrosophic $\mathcal{N}$ -structure X_N over X is a neutrosophic $\mathcal{N}$ -UP-subalgebra of X if and only if for all $\alpha, \beta, \gamma \in [-1, 0]$, the sets $L(T_N; \alpha), U(I_N; \beta)$, and $L(F_N; \gamma)$ are UP-subalgebras of X if $L(T_N; \alpha), U(I_N; \beta)$, and $L(F_N; \gamma)$ are nonempty.

Proof. Assume that X_N is a neutrosophic $\mathcal{N}$ -UP-subalgebra of X . Let $\alpha, \beta, \gamma \in [-1, 0]$ be such that $L(T_N; \alpha), U(I_N; \beta)$, and $L(F_N; \gamma)$ are nonempty.

Let $x, y \in L(T_N; \alpha)$. Then $T_N(x) \leq \alpha$ and $T_N(y) \leq \alpha$, so α is an upper bound of $\{T_N(x), T_N(y)\}$. By (3.2), we have $T_N(x \cdot y) \leq \max\{T_N(x), T_N(y)\} \leq \alpha$. Thus $x \cdot y \in L(T_N; \alpha)$.

Let $x, y \in U(I_N; \beta)$. Then $I_N(x) \geq \beta$ and $I_N(y) \geq \beta$, so β is a lower bound of $\{I_N(x), I_N(y)\}$. By (3.3), we have $I_N(x \cdot y) \geq \min\{I_N(x), I_N(y)\} \geq \beta$. Thus $x \cdot y \in U(I_N; \beta)$.

Let $x, y \in L(F_N; \gamma)$. Then $F_N(x) \leq \gamma$ and $F_N(y) \leq \gamma$, so γ is an upper bound of $\{F_N(x), F_N(y)\}$. By (3.4), we have $F_N(x \cdot y) \leq \max\{F_N(x), F_N(y)\} \leq \gamma$. Thus $x \cdot y \in L(F_N; \gamma)$.

Hence, $L(T_N; \alpha), U(I_N; \beta)$, and $L(F_N; \gamma)$ are UP-subalgebras of X .

Conversely, assume that for all $\alpha, \beta, \gamma \in [-1, 0]$, the sets $L(T_N; \alpha), U(I_N; \beta)$, and $L(F_N; \gamma)$ are UP-subalgebras of X if $L(T_N; \alpha), U(I_N; \beta)$, and $L(F_N; \gamma)$ are nonempty.

Let $x, y \in X$. Then $T_N(x), T_N(y) \in [-1, 0]$. Choose $\alpha = \max\{T_N(x), T_N(y)\}$. Thus $T_N(x) \leq \alpha$ and $T_N(y) \leq \alpha$, so $x, y \in L(T_N; \alpha) \neq \emptyset$. By assumption, we have $L(T_N; \alpha)$ is a UP-subalgebra of X and so $x \cdot y \in L(T_N; \alpha)$. Thus $T_N(x \cdot y) \leq \alpha = \max\{T_N(x), T_N(y)\}$.

Let $x, y \in X$. Then $I_N(x), I_N(y) \in [-1, 0]$. Choose $\beta = \min\{I_N(x), I_N(y)\}$. Thus $I_N(x) \geq \beta$ and $I_N(y) \geq \beta$, so $x, y \in U(I_N; \beta) \neq \emptyset$. By assumption, we have $U(I_N; \beta)$ is a UP-subalgebra of X and so $x \cdot y \in U(I_N; \beta)$. Thus $I_N(x \cdot y) \geq \beta = \min\{I_N(x), I_N(y)\}$.

Let $x, y \in X$. Then $F_N(x), F_N(y) \in [-1, 0]$. Choose $\gamma = \max\{F_N(x), F_N(y)\}$. Thus $F_N(x) \leq \gamma$ and $F_N(y) \leq \gamma$, so $x, y \in L(F_N; \gamma) \neq \emptyset$. By assumption, we have $L(F_N; \gamma)$ is a UP-subalgebra of X and so $x \cdot y \in L(F_N; \gamma)$. Thus $F_N(x \cdot y) \leq \gamma = \max\{F_N(x), F_N(y)\}$.

Therefore, X_N is a neutrosophic $\mathcal{N}$ -UP-subalgebra of X .

Theorem 4.3 A neutrosophic $\mathcal{N}$ -structure X_N over X is a neutrosophic $\mathcal{N}$ -near UP-filter of X if and only if for all $\alpha, \beta, \gamma \in [-1, 0]$, the sets $L(T_N; \alpha), U(I_N; \beta)$, and $L(F_N; \gamma)$ are near UP-filters of X if $L(T_N; \alpha), U(I_N; \beta)$, and $L(F_N; \gamma)$ are nonempty.

Proof. Assume that X_N is a neutrosophic $\mathcal{N}$ -near UP-filter of X . Let $\alpha, \beta, \gamma \in [-1, 0]$ be such that $L(T_N; \alpha), U(I_N; \beta)$, and $L(F_N; \gamma)$ are nonempty.

Let $x \in L(T_N; \alpha)$. Then $T_N(x) \leq \alpha$. By (3.5), we have $T_N(0) \leq T_N(x) \leq \alpha$. Thus $0 \in L(T_N; \alpha)$. Next, let $x \in X$ and $y \in L(T_N; \alpha)$. Then $T_N(y) \leq \alpha$. By (3.8), we have $T_N(x \cdot y) \leq T_N(y) \leq \alpha$. Thus $x \cdot y \in L(T_N; \alpha)$.

Let $x \in U(I_N; \beta)$. Then $I_N(x) \geq \beta$. By (3.6), we have $I_N(0) \geq I_N(x) \geq \beta$. Thus $0 \in U(I_N; \beta)$. Next, let $x \in X$ and $y \in U(I_N; \beta)$. Then $I_N(y) \geq \beta$. By (3.9), we have $I_N(x \cdot y) \geq I_N(y) \geq \beta$. Thus $x \cdot y \in U(I_N; \beta)$.

Let $x \in L(F_N; \gamma)$. Then $F_N(x) \leq \gamma$. By (3.7), we have $F_N(0) \leq F_N(x) \leq \gamma$. Thus $0 \in L(F_N; \gamma)$. Next, let $x \in X$ and $y \in L(F_N; \gamma)$. Then $F_N(y) \leq \gamma$. By (3.10), we have $F_N(x \cdot y) \leq F_N(y) \leq \gamma$. Thus $x \cdot y \in L(F_N; \gamma)$.

Hence, $L(T_N; \alpha), U(I_N; \beta)$, and $L(F_N; \gamma)$ are near UP-filters of X .

Conversely, assume that for all $\alpha, \beta, \gamma \in [-1, 0]$, the sets $L(T_N; \alpha), U(I_N; \beta)$, and $L(F_N; \gamma)$ are near UP-filters of X if $L(T_N; \alpha), U(I_N; \beta)$, and $L(F_N; \gamma)$ are nonempty.

Let $x \in X$. Then $T_N(x) \in [-1, 0]$. Choose $\alpha = T_N(x)$. Thus $T_N(x) \leq \alpha$, so $x \in L(T_N; \alpha) \neq \emptyset$. By assumption, we have $L(T_N; \alpha)$ is a near UP-filter of X and so $0 \in L(T_N; \alpha)$. Thus $T_N(0) \leq \alpha = T_N(x)$. Next, let $x, y \in X$. Then $T_N(y) \in [-1, 0]$. Choose $\alpha = T_N(y)$. Thus $T_N(y) \leq \alpha$, so $y \in L(T_N; \alpha) \neq \emptyset$. By assumption, we have $L(T_N; \alpha)$ is a near UP-filter of X and so $x \cdot y \in L(T_N; \alpha)$. Thus $T_N(x \cdot y) \leq \alpha = T_N(y)$.

Let $x \in X$. Then $I_N(x) \in [-1, 0]$. Choose $\beta = I_N(x)$. Thus $I_N(x) \geq \beta$, so $x \in U(I_N; \beta) \neq \emptyset$. By assumption, we have $U(I_N; \beta)$ is a near UP-filter of X and so $0 \in U(I_N; \beta)$. Thus $I_N(0) \geq \beta = I_N(x)$. Next, let $x, y \in X$. Then $I_N(y) \in [-1, 0]$. Choose $\beta = I_N(y)$. Thus $I_N(y) \geq \beta$, so $y \in U(I_N; \beta) \neq \emptyset$. By assumption, we have $U(I_N; \beta)$ is a near UP-filter of X and so $x \cdot y \in U(I_N; \beta)$. Thus $I_N(x \cdot y) \geq \beta = I_N(y)$.

Let $x \in X$. Then $F_N(x) \in [-1, 0]$. Choose $\gamma = F_N(x)$. Thus $F_N(x) \leq \gamma$, so $x \in L(F_N; \gamma) \neq \emptyset$. By assumption, we have $L(F_N; \gamma)$ is a near UP-filter of X and so $0 \in L(F_N; \gamma)$. Thus

$F_N(0) \leq \gamma = F_N(x)$. Next, let $x, y \in X$. Then $F_N(y) \in [-1, 0]$. Choose $\gamma = F_N(y)$. Thus $F_N(y) \leq \gamma$, so $y \in L(F_N; \gamma) \neq \emptyset$. By assumption, we have $L(F_N; \gamma)$ is a near UP-filter of X and so $x \cdot y \in L(F_N; \gamma)$. Thus $F_N(x \cdot y) \leq \gamma = F_N(y)$.

Therefore, X_N is a neutrosophic $\mathcal{N}$ -near UP-filter of X .

Theorem 4.4 A neutrosophic $\mathcal{N}$ -structure X_N over X is a neutrosophic $\mathcal{N}$ -UP-filter of X if and only if for all $\alpha, \beta, \gamma \in [-1, 0]$, the sets $L(T_N; \alpha), U(I_N; \beta)$, and $L(F_N; \gamma)$ are UP-filters of X if $L(T_N; \alpha), U(I_N; \beta)$, and $L(F_N; \gamma)$ are nonempty.

Proof. Assume that X_N is a neutrosophic $\mathcal{N}$ -UP-filter of X . Let $\alpha, \beta, \gamma \in [-1, 0]$ be such that $L(T_N; \alpha), U(I_N; \beta)$, and $L(F_N; \gamma)$ are nonempty.

Let $x \in L(T_N; \alpha)$. Then $T_N(x) \leq \alpha$. By (3.5), we have $T_N(0) \leq T_N(x) \leq \alpha$. Thus $0 \in L(T_N; \alpha)$. Next, let $x, y \in X$ be such that $x \cdot y \in L(T_N; \alpha)$ and $x \in L(T_N; \alpha)$. Then $T_N(x \cdot y) \leq \alpha$ and $T_N(x) \leq \alpha$, so α is an upper bound of $\{T_N(x \cdot y), T_N(x)\}$. By (3.11), we have $T_N(y) \leq \max\{T_N(x \cdot y), T_N(x)\} \leq \alpha$. Thus $y \in L(T_N; \alpha)$.

Let $x \in U(I_N; \beta)$. Then $I_N(x) \geq \beta$. By (3.5), we have $I_N(0) \geq I_N(x) \geq \beta$. Thus $0 \in U(I_N; \beta)$. Next, let $x, y \in X$ be such that $x \cdot y \in U(I_N; \beta)$ and $x \in U(I_N; \beta)$. Then $I_N(x \cdot y) \geq \beta$ and $I_N(x) \geq \beta$, so β is a lower bound of $\{I_N(x \cdot y), I_N(x)\}$. By (3.12), we have $I_N(y) \geq \min\{I_N(x \cdot y), I_N(x)\} \geq \beta$. Thus $y \in U(I_N; \beta)$.

Let $x \in L(F_N; \gamma)$. Then $F_N(x) \leq \gamma$. By (3.5), we have $F_N(0) \leq F_N(x) \leq \gamma$. Thus $0 \in L(F_N; \gamma)$. Next, let $x, y \in X$ be such that $x \cdot y \in L(F_N; \gamma)$ and $x \in L(F_N; \gamma)$. Next, let $x, y \in L(F_N; \gamma)$ and $x \in L(F_N; \gamma)$. Then $F_N(x \cdot y) \leq \gamma$ and $F_N(x) \leq \gamma$, so γ is an upper bound of $\{F_N(x \cdot y), F_N(x)\}$. By (3.13), we have $F_N(y) \leq \max\{F_N(x \cdot y), F_N(x)\} \leq \gamma$. Thus $y \in L(F_N; \gamma)$.

Hence, $L(T_N; \alpha), U(I_N; \beta)$, and $L(F_N; \gamma)$ are UP-filters of X .

Conversely, assume that for all $\alpha, \beta, \gamma \in [-1, 0]$, the sets $L(T_N; \alpha), U(I_N; \beta)$, and $L(F_N; \gamma)$ are UP-filters of X if $L(T_N; \alpha), U(I_N; \beta)$, and $L(F_N; \gamma)$ are nonempty.

Let $x \in X$. Then $T_N(x) \in [-1, 0]$. Choose $\alpha = T_N(x)$. Thus $T_N(x) \leq \alpha$, so $x \in L(T_N; \alpha) \neq \emptyset$. By assumption, we have $L(T_N; \alpha)$ is a UP-filter of X and so $0 \in L(T_N; \alpha)$. Thus $T_N(0) \leq \alpha = T_N(x)$. Next, let $x, y \in X$. Then $T_N(x \cdot y), T_N(x) \in [-1, 0]$. Choose $\alpha = \max\{T_N(x \cdot y), T_N(x)\}$. Thus $T_N(x \cdot y) \leq \alpha$ and $T_N(x) \leq \alpha$, so $x \cdot y, x \in L(T_N; \alpha) \neq \emptyset$. By assumption, we have $L(T_N; \alpha)$ is a UP-filter of X and so $y \in L(T_N; \alpha)$. Thus $T_N(y) \leq \alpha = \max\{T_N(x \cdot y), T_N(x)\}$.

Let $x \in X$. Then $I_N(x) \in [-1, 0]$. Choose $\beta = I_N(x)$. Thus $I_N(x) \geq \beta$, so $x \in U(I_N; \beta) \neq \emptyset$. By assumption, we have $U(I_N; \beta)$ is a UP-filter of X and so $0 \in U(I_N; \beta)$. Thus $I_N(0) \geq \beta = I_N(x)$. Next, let $x, y \in X$. Then $I_N(x \cdot y), I_N(x) \in [-1, 0]$. Choose $\beta = \min\{I_N(x \cdot y), I_N(x)\}$. Thus $I_N(x \cdot y) \geq \beta$ and $I_N(x) \geq \beta$, so $x \cdot y, x \in U(I_N; \beta) \neq \emptyset$. By assumption, we have $U(I_N; \beta)$ is a UP-filter of X and so $y \in U(I_N; \beta)$. Thus $I_N(y) \geq \beta = \min\{I_N(x \cdot y), I_N(x)\}$.

Let $x \in X$. Then $F_N(x) \in [-1, 0]$. Choose $\gamma = F_N(x)$. Thus $F_N(x) \leq \gamma$, so $x \in L(F_N; \gamma) \neq \emptyset$. By assumption, we have $L(F_N; \gamma)$ is a UP-filter of X and so $0 \in L(F_N; \gamma)$. Thus $F_N(0) \leq \gamma = F_N(x)$. Next, let $x, y \in X$. Then $F_N(x \cdot y), F_N(x) \in [-1, 0]$. Choose $\gamma = \max\{F_N(x \cdot y), F_N(x)\}$. Thus $F_N(x \cdot y) \leq \gamma$ and $F_N(x) \leq \gamma$, so $x \cdot y, x \in L(F_N; \gamma) \neq \emptyset$. By assumption, we have $L(F_N; \gamma)$ is a UP-filter of X and so $y \in L(F_N; \gamma)$. Thus $F_N(y) \leq \gamma = \max\{F_N(x \cdot y), F_N(x)\}$.

Therefore, X_N is a neutrosophic $\mathcal{N}$ -UP-filter of X .

Theorem 4.5 A neutrosophic $\mathcal{N}$ -structure X_N over X is a neutrosophic $\mathcal{N}$ -UP-ideal of X if and only if for all $\alpha, \beta, \gamma \in [-1, 0]$, the sets $L(T_N; \alpha), U(I_N; \beta)$, and $L(F_N; \gamma)$ are UP-ideals of X if $L(T_N; \alpha), U(I_N; \beta)$, and $L(F_N; \gamma)$ are nonempty.

Proof. Assume that X_N is a neutrosophic $\mathcal{N}$ -UP-ideal of X . Let $\alpha, \beta, \gamma \in [-1, 0]$ be such that $L(T_N; \alpha), U(I_N; \beta)$, and $L(F_N; \gamma)$ are nonempty.

Let $x \in L(T_N; \alpha)$. Then $T_N(x) \leq \alpha$. By (3.5), we have $T_N(0) \leq T_N(x) \leq \alpha$. Thus $0 \in L(T_N; \alpha)$. Next, let $x, y, z \in X$ be such that $x \cdot (y \cdot z) \in L(T_N; \alpha)$ and $y \in L(T_N; \alpha)$. Then $T_N(x \cdot (y \cdot z)) \leq \alpha$ and $T_N(y) \leq \alpha$, so α is an upper bound of $\{T_N(x \cdot (y \cdot z)), T_N(y)\}$. By (3.14), we have $T_N(x \cdot z) \leq \max\{T_N(x \cdot (y \cdot z)), T_N(y)\} \leq \alpha$. Thus $x \cdot z \in L(T_N; \alpha)$.

Let $x \in U(I_N; \alpha)$. Then $I_N(x) \geq \beta$. By (3.5), we have $I_N(0) \geq I_N(x) \geq \beta$. Thus $0 \in U(I_N; \beta)$. Next, let $x, y, z \in X$ be such that $x \cdot (y \cdot z) \in U(I_N; \beta)$ and $y \in U(I_N; \beta)$. Then $I_N(x \cdot (y \cdot z)) \geq \beta$ and $I_N(y) \geq \beta$, so β is a lower bound of $\{I_N(x \cdot (y \cdot z)), I_N(y)\}$. By (3.15), we have $I_N(x \cdot z) \geq \min\{I_N(x \cdot (y \cdot z)), I_N(y)\} \geq \beta$. Thus $x \cdot z \in U(I_N; \beta)$.

Let $x \in L(F_N; \gamma)$. Then $F_N(x) \leq \gamma$. By (3.5), we have $F_N(0) \leq F_N(x) \leq \gamma$. Thus $0 \in L(F_N; \gamma)$. Next, let $x, y, z \in X$ be such that $x \cdot (y \cdot z) \in L(F_N; \gamma)$ and $y \in L(F_N; \gamma)$. Then $F_N(x \cdot (y \cdot z)) \leq \gamma$ and $F_N(y) \leq \gamma$, so γ is an upper bound of $\{F_N(x \cdot (y \cdot z)), F_N(y)\}$. By (3.16), we have $F_N(x \cdot z) \leq \max\{F_N(x \cdot (y \cdot z)), F_N(y)\} \leq \gamma$. Thus $x \cdot z \in L(F_N; \gamma)$.

Hence, $L(T_N; \alpha), U(I_N; \beta)$, and $L(F_N; \gamma)$ are UP-ideals of X .

Conversely, assume that for all $\alpha, \beta, \gamma \in [-1, 0]$, the sets $L(T_N; \alpha), U(I_N; \beta)$, and $L(F_N; \gamma)$ are UP-ideals of X if $L(T_N; \alpha), U(I_N; \beta)$, and $L(F_N; \gamma)$ are nonempty.

Let $x \in X$. Then $T_N(x) \in [-1, 0]$. Choose $\alpha = T_N(x)$. Thus $T_N(x) \leq \alpha$, so $x \in L(T_N; \alpha) \neq \emptyset$. By assumption, we have $L(T_N; \alpha)$ is a UP-ideal of X and so $0 \in L(T_N; \alpha)$. Thus $T_N(0) \leq \alpha = T_N(x)$. Next, let $x, y, z \in X$. Then $T_N(x \cdot (y \cdot z)), T_N(y) \in [-1, 0]$. Choose $\alpha = \max\{T_N(x \cdot (y \cdot z)), T_N(y)\}$. Thus $T_N(x \cdot (y \cdot z)) \leq \alpha$ and $T_N(y) \leq \alpha$, so $x \cdot (y \cdot z), y \in L(T_N; \alpha) \neq \emptyset$. By assumption, we have $L(T_N; \alpha)$ is a UP-ideal of X and so $x \cdot z \in L(T_N; \alpha)$. Thus $T_N(x \cdot z) \leq \alpha = \max\{T_N(x \cdot (y \cdot z)), T_N(y)\}$.

Let $x \in X$. Then $I_N(x) \in [-1, 0]$. Choose $\beta = I_N(x)$. Thus $I_N(x) \geq \beta$, so $x \in U(I_N; \beta) \neq \emptyset$. By assumption, we have $U(I_N; \beta)$ is a UP-ideal of X and so $0 \in U(I_N; \beta)$. Thus $I_N(0) \geq \beta = I_N(x)$. Next, let $x, y, z \in X$. Then $I_N(x \cdot (y \cdot z)), I_N(y) \in [-1, 0]$. Choose $\beta = \min\{I_N(x \cdot (y \cdot z)), I_N(y)\}$. Thus $I_N(x \cdot (y \cdot z)) \geq \beta$ and $I_N(y) \geq \beta$, so $x \cdot (y \cdot z), y \in U(I_N; \beta) \neq \emptyset$. By assumption, we have $U(I_N; \beta)$ is a UP-ideal of X and so $x \cdot z \in U(I_N; \beta)$. Thus $I_N(x \cdot z) \geq \beta = \min\{I_N(x \cdot (y \cdot z)), I_N(y)\}$.

Let $x \in X$. Then $F_N(x) \in [-1, 0]$. Choose $\gamma = F_N(x)$. Thus $F_N(x) \leq \gamma$, so $x \in L(F_N; \gamma) \neq \emptyset$. By assumption, we have $L(F_N; \gamma)$ is a UP-ideal of X and so $0 \in L(F_N; \gamma)$. Thus $F_N(0) \leq \gamma = F_N(x)$. Next, let $x, y, z \in X$. Then $F_N(x \cdot (y \cdot z)), F_N(y) \in [-1, 0]$. Choose $\gamma = \max\{F_N(x \cdot (y \cdot z)), F_N(y)\}$. Thus $F_N(x \cdot (y \cdot z)) \leq \gamma$ and $F_N(y) \leq \gamma$, so $x \cdot (y \cdot z), y \in L(F_N; \gamma) \neq \emptyset$. By assumption, we have $L(F_N; \gamma)$ is a UP-ideal of X and so $x \cdot z \in L(F_N; \gamma)$. Thus $F_N(x \cdot z) \leq \gamma = \max\{F_N(x \cdot (y \cdot z)), F_N(y)\}$.

Therefore, X_N is a neutrosophic $\mathcal{N}$ -UP-ideal of X .

Theorem 4.6 A neutrosophic $\mathcal{N}$ -structure X_N over X is a neutrosophic $\mathcal{N}$ -strongly UP-ideal of X if and only if the sets $E(T_N; T_N(0)), E(I_N; I_N(0))$, and $E(F_N; F_N(0))$ are strongly UP-ideals of X .

Proof. Assume that X_N is a neutrosophic $\mathcal{N}$ -strongly UP-ideal of X . By Theorem 3.17, we have X_N is constant, that is, T_N, I_N , and F_N are constant. Thus

$$(\forall x \in X) \begin{pmatrix} T_N(x) = T_N(0) \\ I_N(x) = I_N(0) \\ F_N(x) = F_N(0) \end{pmatrix}.$$

Hence, $E(T_N; T_N(0)) = X, E(I_N; I_N(0)) = X$, and $E(F_N; F_N(0)) = X$ and so $E(T_N; T_N(0)), E(I_N; I_N(0))$, and $E(F_N; F_N(0))$ are strongly UP-ideals of X .

Conversely, assume that $E(T_N; T_N(0)), E(I_N; I_N(0))$, and $E(F_N; F_N(0))$ are strongly UP-ideals of X . Then $E(T_N; T_N(0)) = X, E(I_N; I_N(0)) = X$, $E(F_N; F_N(0)) = X$ and so

$$(\forall x \in X) \begin{pmatrix} T_N(x) = T_N(0) \\ I_N(x) = I_N(0) \\ F_N(x) = F_N(0) \end{pmatrix}.$$

Thus T_N, I_N , and F_N are constant, that is X_N is constant. By Theorem 3.17, we have X_N is a neutrosophic $\mathcal{N}$ -strongly UP-ideal of X .

5. Neutrosophic $\mathcal{N}$ -structures of special type

In this section, we introduce the notions of special neutrosophic $\mathcal{N}$ -UP-subalgebras, special neutrosophic $\mathcal{N}$ -near UP-filters, special neutrosophic $\mathcal{N}$ -UP-filters, special neutrosophic $\mathcal{N}$ -UP-ideals, and special neutrosophic $\mathcal{N}$ -strongly UP-ideals of UP-algebras, provide the necessary examples, investigate their properties, and prove their generalizations.

Definition 5.1 A neutrosophic $\mathcal{N}$ -structure X_N over X is called a *special neutrosophic $\mathcal{N}$ -UP-subalgebra* of X if it satisfies the following conditions:

$$(\forall x, y \in X)(T_N(x \cdot y) \geq \min\{T_N(x), T_N(y)\}), \tag{5.1}$$

$$(\forall x, y \in X)(I_N(x \cdot y) \leq \max\{I_N(x), I_N(y)\}), \tag{5.2}$$

$$(\forall x, y \in X)(F_N(x \cdot y) \geq \min\{F_N(x), F_N(y)\}). \tag{5.3}$$

Example 5.2 Let $X = \{0,1,2,3,4\}$ be a set with a binary operation $\cdot$ defined by the following Cayley table:

$\cdot$	0	1	2	3	4
0	0	1	2	3	4
1	0	0	2	3	0
2	0	1	0	0	0
3	0	1	2	0	0
4	0	1	2	3	0

Then $(X, \cdot, 0)$ is a UP-algebra. We define a neutrosophic $\mathcal{N}$ -structure X_N over X as follows:

$$T_N(0) = -0.2, I_N(0) = -0.9, F_N(0) = -0.2,$$

$$T_N(1) = -0.4, I_N(1) = -0.8, F_N(1) = -0.4,$$

$$T_N(2) = -0.8, I_N(2) = -0.7, F_N(2) = -0.6,$$

$$T_N(3) = -0.3, I_N(3) = -0.5, F_N(3) = -0.7,$$

$$T_N(4) = -0.8, I_N(4) = -0.3, F_N(4) = -0.8.$$

Hence, X_N is a special neutrosophic $\mathcal{N}$ -UP-subalgebra of X .

Definition 5.3 A neutrosophic $\mathcal{N}^c$ -structure X_N over X is called a *special neutrosophic $\mathcal{N}^c$ -near UP-filter* of X if it satisfies the following conditions:

$$(\forall x \in X)(T_N(0) \geq T_N(x)), \tag{5.4}$$

$$(\forall x \in X)(I_N(0) \leq I_N(x)), \tag{5.5}$$

$$(\forall x \in X)(F_N(0) \geq F_N(x)), \tag{5.6}$$

$$(\forall x, y \in X)(T_N(x \cdot y) \geq T_N(y)), \tag{5.7}$$

$$(\forall x, y \in X)(I_N(x \cdot y) \leq I_N(y)), \tag{5.8}$$

$$(\forall x, y \in X)(F_N(x \cdot y) \geq F_N(y)). \tag{5.9}$$

Example 5.4 Let $X = \{0,1,2,3,4\}$ be a set with a binary operation $\cdot$ defined by the following Cayley table:

$\cdot$	0	1	2	3	4
0	0	1	2	3	4
1	0	0	0	3	0
2	0	2	0	3	0
3	0	2	2	0	0
4	0	2	2	3	0

Then $(X, \cdot, 0)$ is a UP-algebra. We define a neutrosophic $\mathcal{N}^c$ -structure X_N over X as follows:

$$T_N(0) = -0.2, I_N(0) = -0.8, F_N(0) = -0.3,$$

$$T_N(1) = -0.5, I_N(1) = -0.5, F_N(1) = -0.7,$$

$$T_N(2) = -0.4, I_N(2) = -0.7, F_N(2) = -0.4,$$

$$T_N(3) = -0.3, I_N(3) = -0.4, F_N(3) = -0.6,$$

$$T_N(4) = -0.8, I_N(4) = -0.2, F_N(4) = -0.8.$$

Hence, X_N is a special neutrosophic $\mathcal{N}^c$ -near UP-filter of X .

Definition 5.5 A neutrosophic $\mathcal{N}^c$ -structure X_N over X is called a *special neutrosophic $\mathcal{N}^c$ -UP-filter* of X if it satisfies the following conditions: (5.4), (5.5), (5.6), and

$$(\forall x, y \in X)(T_N(y) \geq \min\{T_N(x \cdot y), T_N(x)\}), \tag{5.10}$$

$$(\forall x, y \in X)(I_N(y) \leq \max\{I_N(x \cdot y), I_N(x)\}), \tag{5.11}$$

$$(\forall x, y \in X)(F_N(y) \geq \min\{F_N(x \cdot y), F_N(x)\}). \tag{5.12}$$

Example 5.6 Let $X = \{0,1,2,3,4\}$ be a set with a binary operation $\cdot$ defined by the following Cayley table:

$\cdot$	0	1	2	3	4
0	0	1	2	3	4
1	0	0	2	3	0
2	0	1	0	3	0
3	0	1	2	0	0
4	0	1	2	3	0

Then $(X, \cdot, 0)$ is a UP-algebra. We define a neutrosophic $\mathcal{N}^c$ -structure X_N over X as follows:

$$T_N(0) = -0.2, I_N(0) = -0.8, F_N(0) = -0.2,$$

$$T_N(1) = -0.8, I_N(1) = -0.5, F_N(1) = -0.8,$$

$$T_N(2) = -0.6, I_N(2) = -0.4, F_N(2) = -0.5,$$

$$T_N(3) = -0.7, I_N(3) = -0.6, F_N(3) = -0.7,$$

$$T_N(4) = -0.5, I_N(4) = -0.7, F_N(4) = -0.4.$$

Hence, X_N is a special neutrosophic $\mathcal{N}$ -UP-filter of X .

Definition 5.7 A neutrosophic $\mathcal{N}$ -structure X_N over X is called a *special neutrosophic $\mathcal{N}$ -UP-ideal* of X if it satisfies the following conditions: (5.4), (5.5), (5.6), and

$$(\forall x, y, z \in X)(T_N(x \cdot z) \geq \min\{T_N(x \cdot (y \cdot z)), T_N(y)\}), \tag{5.13}$$

$$(\forall x, y, z \in X)(I_N(x \cdot z) \leq \max\{I_N(x \cdot (y \cdot z)), I_N(y)\}), \tag{5.14}$$

$$(\forall x, y, z \in X)(F_N(x \cdot z) \geq \min\{F_N(x \cdot (y \cdot z)), F_N(y)\}). \tag{5.15}$$

Example 5.8 Let $X = \{0,1,2,3,4\}$ be a set with a binary operation $\cdot$ defined by the following Cayley table:

$\cdot$	0	1	2	3	4
0	0	1	2	3	4
1	0	0	2	0	4
2	0	0	0	0	0
3	0	3	2	0	4
4	0	3	2	0	0

Then $(X, \cdot, 0)$ is a UP-algebra. We define a neutrosophic $\mathcal{N}$ -structure X_N over X as follows:

$$T_N(0) = -0.3, I_N(0) = -0.8, F_N(0) = -0.2,$$

$$T_N(1) = -0.6, I_N(1) = -0.6, F_N(1) = -0.3,$$

$$T_N(2) = -0.8, I_N(2) = -0.4, F_N(2) = -0.8,$$

$$T_N(3) = -0.6, I_N(3) = -0.6, F_N(3) = -0.3,$$

$$T_N(4) = -0.7, I_N(4) = -0.5, F_N(4) = -0.7.$$

Hence, X_N is a special neutrosophic $\mathcal{N}$ -UP-ideal of X .

Definition 5.9 A neutrosophic $\mathcal{N}$ -structure X_N over X is called a *special neutrosophic $\mathcal{N}$ -strongly UP-ideal* of X if it satisfies the following conditions: (5.4), (5.5), (5.6), and

$$(\forall x, y, z \in X)(T_N(x) \geq \min\{T_N((z \cdot y) \cdot (z \cdot x)), T_N(y)\}), \tag{5.16}$$

$$(\forall x, y, z \in X)(I_N(x) \leq \max\{I_N((z \cdot y) \cdot (z \cdot x)), I_N(y)\}), \tag{5.17}$$

$$(\forall x, y, z \in X)(F_N(x) \geq \min\{F_N((z \cdot y) \cdot (z \cdot x)), F_N(y)\}). \tag{5.18}$$

Example 5.10 Let $X = \{0,1,2,3,4\}$ be a set with a binary operation $\cdot$ defined by the following Cayley table:

$\cdot$	0	1	2	3	4
0	0	1	2	3	4
1	0	0	2	3	0
2	0	1	0	0	4
3	0	1	2	0	4
4	0	4	2	3	0

Then $(X, \cdot, 0)$ is a UP-algebra. We define a neutrosophic $\mathcal{N}$ -structure X_N over X as follows:

$$(\forall x \in X) \begin{pmatrix} T_N(x) = -0.5 \\ I_N(x) = -1 \\ F_N(x) = -0.3 \end{pmatrix}.$$

Hence, X_N is a special neutrosophic $\mathcal{N}$ -strongly UP-ideal X .

Theorem 5.11 Every special neutrosophic $\mathcal{N}$ -UP-subalgebra of X satisfies the conditions (5.4), (5.5), and (5.6).

Proof. Assume that X_N is a special neutrosophic $\mathcal{N}$ -UP-subalgebra of X . Then for all $x \in X$, by Proposition 2.5 (1), (5.1), (5.2), and (5.3), we have

$$T_N(0) = T_N(x \cdot x) \geq \min\{T_N(x), T_N(x)\} = T_N(x), \quad I_N(0) = I_N(x \cdot x) \leq \max\{I_N(x), I_N(x)\} = I_N(x),$$

$$F_N(0) = F_N(x \cdot x) \geq \min\{F_N(x), F_N(x)\} = F_N(x).$$

Hence, X_N satisfies the conditions (5.4), (5.5), and (5.6).

By Lemma 3.4 (1) and (4), we have the following five theorems.

Theorem 5.12 A neutrosophic $\mathcal{N}$ -structure X_N over X is a neutrosophic $\mathcal{N}$ -UP-subalgebra of X if and only if $\overline{X}_N$ is a special neutrosophic $\mathcal{N}$ -UP-subalgebra of X .

Theorem 5.13 A neutrosophic $\mathcal{N}$ -structure X_N over X is a neutrosophic $\mathcal{N}$ -near UP-filter of X if and only if $\overline{X}_N$ is a special neutrosophic $\mathcal{N}$ -near UP-filter of X .

Theorem 5.14 A neutrosophic $\mathcal{N}$ -structure X_N over X is a neutrosophic $\mathcal{N}$ -UP-filter of X if and only if $\overline{X}_N$ is a special neutrosophic $\mathcal{N}$ -UP-filter of X .

Theorem 5.15 A neutrosophic $\mathcal{N}$ -structure X_N over X is a neutrosophic $\mathcal{N}$ -UP-ideal of X if and only if $\overline{X}_N$ is a special neutrosophic $\mathcal{N}$ -UP-ideal of X .

Theorem 5.16 A neutrosophic $\mathcal{N}$ -structure X_N over X is a neutrosophic $\mathcal{N}$ -strongly UP-ideal of X if and only if $\overline{X}_N$ is a special neutrosophic $\mathcal{N}$ -strongly UP-ideal of X .

Theorem 5.17 A neutrosophic $\mathcal{N}$ -structure X_N over X is constant if and only if it is a special neutrosophic $\mathcal{N}$ -strongly UP-ideal of X .

Proof. It is straightforward by Remark 3.2 and Theorems 3.17 and 5.16.

By Remark Remark 3.2 and Theorems 5.12, 5.13, 5.14, 5.15, and 5.16, we have that the notion of special neutrosophic $\mathcal{N}$ -UP-subalgebras is a generalization of special neutrosophic $\mathcal{N}$ -near UP-filters, special neutrosophic $\mathcal{N}$ -near UP-filters is a generalization of special neutrosophic $\mathcal{N}$ -UP-filters, special neutrosophic $\mathcal{N}$ -UP-filters is a generalization of special neutrosophic $\mathcal{N}$ -UP-ideals, and special neutrosophic $\mathcal{N}$ -UP-ideals is a generalization of special neutrosophic $\mathcal{N}$ -strongly UP-ideals. Moreover, by Theorem 5.17, we obtain that special neutrosophic $\mathcal{N}$ -strongly UP-ideals and constant neutrosophic $\mathcal{N}$ -structures coincide.

Theorem 5.18 If X_N is a special neutrosophic $\mathcal{N}$ -UP-subalgebra of X satisfying the following condition:

$$(\forall x, y \in X) \left(x \cdot y \neq 0 \Rightarrow \begin{cases} T_N(x) \geq T_N(y) \\ I_N(x) \leq I_N(y) \\ F_N(x) \geq F_N(y) \end{cases} \right), \tag{5.19}$$

then X_N is a special neutrosophic $\mathcal{N}$ -near UP-filter of X .

Proof. Assume that X_N is a special neutrosophic $\mathcal{N}$ -UP-subalgebra of X satisfying the condition (5.19). By Theorem 5.11, we have X_N satisfies the conditions (5.4), (5.5), and (5.6). Next, let $x, y \in X$.

Case 1: $x \cdot y = 0$. Then, by (5.4), (5.5), and (5.6), we have

$$T_N(x \cdot y) = T_N(0) \geq T_N(y), \quad I_N(x \cdot y) = I_N(0) \leq I_N(y), \quad F_N(x \cdot y) = F_N(0) \geq F_N(y).$$

Case 2: $x \cdot y \neq 0$. Then, by (5.1), (5.2), (5.3), and (5.19), we have

$$T_N(x \cdot y) \geq \min\{T_N(x), T_N(y)\} = T_N(y), \quad I_N(x \cdot y) \leq \max\{I_N(x), I_N(y)\} = I_N(y),$$

$$F_N(x \cdot y) \geq \min\{F_N(x), F_N(y)\} = F_N(y).$$

Hence, X_N is a special neutrosophic $\mathcal{N}$ -near UP-filter of X .

Theorem 5.19 If X_N is a special neutrosophic $\mathcal{N}$ -near UP-filter of X satisfying the condition (3.21), then X_N is a special neutrosophic $\mathcal{N}$ -UP-filter of X .

Proof. Assume that X_N is a special neutrosophic $\mathcal{N}$ -near UP-filter of X satisfying the condition (3.21). Then X_N satisfies the conditions (5.4), (5.5), and (5.6). Next, let $x, y, z \in X$. By (5.7), (5.8), and (3.21), we have

$$\min\{T_N(x \cdot y), T_N(x)\} = \min\{I_N(x \cdot y), T_N(x)\} \leq \min\{I_N(y), T_N(x)\} = \min\{T_N(y), T_N(x)\} \leq T_N(y),$$

$$\max\{I_N(x \cdot y), I_N(x)\} = \max\{T_N(x \cdot y), I_N(x)\} \geq \max\{T_N(y), I_N(x)\} = \max\{I_N(y), I_N(x)\} \geq I_N(y),$$

$$\min\{F_N(x \cdot y), F_N(x)\} = \min\{I_N(x \cdot y), F_N(x)\} \leq \min\{I_N(y), F_N(x)\} = \min\{F_N(y), F_N(x)\} \leq F_N(y).$$

Hence, X_N is a special neutrosophic $\mathcal{N}$ -UP-filter of X .

Theorem 5.20 If X_N is a special neutrosophic $\mathcal{N}$ -UP-filter of X satisfying the condition (3.22), then X_N is a special neutrosophic $\mathcal{N}$ -UP-ideal of X .

Proof. Assume that X_N is a special neutrosophic $\mathcal{N}$ -UP-filter of X satisfying the condition (3.22). Then X_N satisfies the conditions (5.4), (5.5), and (5.6). Next, let $x, y, z \in X$. By (5.10), (5.11), (5.12), and (3.22), we have

$$T_N(x \cdot z) \geq \min\{T_N(y \cdot (x \cdot z)), T_N(y)\} = \min\{T_N(x \cdot (y \cdot z)), T_N(y)\},$$

$$I_N(x \cdot z) \leq \max\{I_N(y \cdot (x \cdot z)), I_N(y)\} = \max\{I_N(x \cdot (y \cdot z)), I_N(y)\},$$

$$F_N(x \cdot z) \geq \min\{F_N(y \cdot (x \cdot z)), F_N(y)\} = \min\{F_N(x \cdot (y \cdot z)), F_N(y)\}.$$

Hence, X_N is a special neutrosophic $\mathcal{N}$ -UP-ideal of X .

Theorem 5.21 If X_N is a neutrosophic $\mathcal{N}$ -structure over X satisfying the following condition:

$$(\forall x, y, z \in X) \left(z \leq x \cdot y \Rightarrow \begin{cases} T_N(z) \geq \min\{T_N(x), T_N(y)\} \\ I_N(z) \leq \max\{I_N(x), I_N(y)\} \\ F_N(z) \geq \min\{F_N(x), F_N(y)\} \end{cases} \right), \quad (5.20)$$

then X_N is a special neutrosophic $\mathcal{N}$ -UP-subalgebra of X .

Proof. Assume that X_N is a neutrosophic $\mathcal{N}$ -structure over X satisfying the condition (5.20). Let $x, y \in X$. By Proposition 2.5 (1), we have $(x \cdot y) \cdot (x \cdot y) = 0$, that is, $x \cdot y \leq x \cdot y$. It follows from (5.20) that

$$T_N(x \cdot y) \geq \min\{T_N(x), T_N(y)\}, \quad I_N(x \cdot y) \leq \max\{I_N(x), I_N(y)\}, \quad F_N(x \cdot y) \geq \min\{F_N(x), F_N(y)\}.$$

Hence, X_N is a special neutrosophic $\mathcal{N}$ -UP-subalgebra of X .

Theorem 5.22 If X_N is a neutrosophic $\mathcal{N}$ -structure over X satisfying the following condition:

$$(\forall x, y, z \in X) \left(z \leq x \cdot y \Rightarrow \begin{cases} T_N(z) \geq T_N(y) \\ I_N(z) \leq I_N(y) \\ F_N(z) \geq F_N(y) \end{cases} \right), \quad (5.21)$$

then X_N is a special neutrosophic $\mathcal{N}$ -near UP-filter of X .

Proof. Assume that X_N is a neutrosophic $\mathcal{N}$ -structure over X satisfying the condition (5.21). Let $x \in X$. By (UP-2) and Proposition 2.5 (1), we have $0 \cdot (x \cdot x) = 0$, that is, $0 \leq x \cdot x$. It follows from (5.21) that $T_N(0) \geq T_N(x), I_N(0) \leq I_N(x)$, and $F_N(0) \geq F_N(x)$. Next, let $x, y \in X$. By Proposition 2.5 (1), we have $(x \cdot y) \cdot (x \cdot y) = 0$, that is, $x \cdot y \leq x \cdot y$. It follows from (5.21) that $T_N(x \cdot y) \geq T_N(y), I_N(x \cdot y) \leq I_N(y)$, and $F_N(x \cdot y) \geq F_N(y)$. Hence, X_N is a special neutrosophic $\mathcal{N}$ -near UP-filter of X .

Theorem 5.23 If X_N is a neutrosophic $\mathcal{N}$ -structure over X satisfying the following condition:

$$(\forall x, y, z \in X) \left(z \leq x \cdot y \Rightarrow \begin{cases} T_N(y) \geq \min\{T_N(z), T_N(x)\} \\ I_N(y) \leq \max\{I_N(z), I_N(x)\} \\ F_N(y) \geq \min\{F_N(z), F_N(x)\} \end{cases} \right), \tag{5.22}$$

then X_N is a special neutrosophic $\mathcal{N}$ -UP-filter of X .

Proof. Assume that X_N is a neutrosophic $\mathcal{N}$ -structure over X satisfying the condition (5.22). Let $x \in X$. By (UP-3), we have $x \cdot (x \cdot 0) = 0$, that is, $x \leq x \cdot 0$. It follows from (5.22) that

$$T_N(0) \geq \min\{T_N(x), T_N(x)\} = T_N(x), I_N(0) \leq \max\{I_N(x), I_N(x)\} = I_N(x), F_N(0) \geq \min\{F_N(x), F_N(x)\} = F_N(x).$$

Next, let $x, y \in X$. By Proposition 2.5 (1), we have $(x \cdot y) \cdot (x \cdot y) = 0$, that is, $x \cdot y \leq x \cdot y$. It follows from (5.22) that

$$T_N(y) \geq \min\{T_N(x \cdot y), T_N(x)\}, I_N(y) \leq \max\{I_N(x \cdot y), I_N(x)\}, F_N(y) \geq \min\{F_N(x \cdot y), F_N(x)\}.$$

Hence, X_N is a special neutrosophic $\mathcal{N}$ -UP-filter of X .

Theorem 5.24 If X_N is a neutrosophic $\mathcal{N}$ -structure over X satisfying the following condition:

$$(\forall a, x, y, z \in X) \left(a \leq x \cdot (y \cdot z) \Rightarrow \begin{cases} T_N(x \cdot z) \geq \min\{T_N(a), T_N(y)\} \\ I_N(x \cdot z) \leq \max\{I_N(a), I_N(y)\} \\ F_N(x \cdot z) \geq \min\{F_N(a), F_N(y)\} \end{cases} \right), \tag{5.23}$$

then X_N is a special neutrosophic $\mathcal{N}$ -UP-ideal of X .

Proof. Assume that X_N is a neutrosophic $\mathcal{N}$ -structure over X satisfying the condition (5.23). Let $x \in X$. By (UP-3), we have $x \cdot (0 \cdot (x \cdot 0)) = 0$, that is, $x \leq 0 \cdot (x \cdot 0)$. It follows from (5.23) and (UP-2) that

$$T_N(0) = T_N(0 \cdot 0) \geq \min\{T_N(x), T_N(x)\} = T_N(x), I_N(0) = I_N(0 \cdot 0) \leq \max\{I_N(x), I_N(x)\} = I_N(x),$$

$$F_N(0) = F_N(0 \cdot 0) \geq \min\{F_N(x), F_N(x)\} = F_N(x).$$

Next, let $x, y, z \in X$. By Proposition 2.5 (1), we have $(x \cdot (y \cdot z)) \cdot (x \cdot (y \cdot z)) = 0$, that is, $x \cdot (y \cdot z) \leq x \cdot (y \cdot z)$. It follows from (5.23) that

$$T_N(x \cdot z) \geq \min\{T_N(x \cdot (y \cdot z)), T_N(y)\}, I_N(x \cdot z) \leq \max\{I_N(x \cdot (y \cdot z)), I_N(y)\},$$

$$F_N(x \cdot z) \geq \min\{F_N(x \cdot (y \cdot z)), F_N(y)\}.$$

Hence, X_N is a special neutrosophic $\mathcal{N}$ -UP-ideal of X .

For any fixed numbers $\alpha^-, \alpha^+, \beta^-, \beta^+, \gamma^-, \gamma^+ \in [-1, 0]$ such that $\alpha^- < \alpha^+, \beta^- < \beta^+, \gamma^- < \gamma^+$ and a nonempty subset G of X , a neutrosophic $\mathcal{N}$ -structure

${}^G X_N[\alpha^-, \beta^+, \gamma^-] = (X, {}^G T_N[\alpha^-], {}^G I_N[\beta^+], {}^G F_N[\gamma^-])$ over X where ${}^G T_N[\alpha^-], {}^G I_N[\beta^+]$, and ${}^G F_N[\gamma^-]$ are

$\mathcal{N}$ -functions on X which are given as follows:

$${}^G T_N[\alpha^+](x) = \begin{cases} \alpha^+ & \text{if } x \in G, \\ \alpha^- & \text{otherwise,} \end{cases} \quad {}^G I_N[\beta^+](x) = \begin{cases} \beta^- & \text{if } x \in G, \\ \beta^+ & \text{otherwise,} \end{cases} \quad {}^G F_N[\gamma^-](x) = \begin{cases} \gamma^+ & \text{if } x \in G, \\ \gamma^- & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases}$$

Lemma 5.25 Let $\alpha^-, \alpha^+, \beta^-, \beta^+, \gamma^-, \gamma^+ \in [-1, 0]$. Then the following statements hold:

1. $\overline{{}^G T_N[\alpha^+, \beta^-, \gamma^+]} = {}^G X_N[-1-\alpha^+, -1-\beta^-, -1-\gamma^+]$, and
2. ${}^G \overline{{}^G X_N[\alpha^+, \beta^+, \gamma^-]} = X_N^G[-1-\alpha^+, -1-\beta^-, -1-\gamma^-]$.

Proof. 1. Let $\overline{{}^G X_N[\alpha^+, \beta^-, \gamma^+]}$ be a neutrosophic $\mathcal{N}^c$ -structure over X . Then

$$\overline{{}^G X_N[\alpha^+, \beta^-, \gamma^+]} = (\overline{{}^G T_N[\alpha^+]}, \overline{{}^G I_N[\beta^+]}, \overline{{}^G F_N[\gamma^+]}) . \text{ Since}$$

$${}^G T_N[\alpha^+](x) = \begin{cases} \alpha^- & \text{if } x \in G, \\ \alpha^+ & \text{otherwise,} \end{cases} \quad {}^G I_N[\beta^+](x) = \begin{cases} \beta^+ & \text{if } x \in G, \\ \beta^- & \text{otherwise,} \end{cases} \quad {}^G F_N[\gamma^+](x) = \begin{cases} \gamma^- & \text{if } x \in G, \\ \gamma^+ & \text{otherwise,} \end{cases} ,$$

we have

$$\overline{{}^G T_N[\alpha^+]}(x) = \begin{cases} -1-\alpha^- & \text{if } x \in G, \\ -1-\alpha^+ & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} = {}^G T_N[-1-\alpha^+](x), \quad \overline{{}^G I_N[\beta^+]}(x) = \begin{cases} -1-\beta^+ & \text{if } x \in G, \\ -1-\beta^- & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} = {}^G I_N[-1-\beta^-](x),$$

$$\overline{{}^G F_N[\gamma^+]}(x) = \begin{cases} -1-\gamma^- & \text{if } x \in G, \\ -1-\gamma^+ & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} = {}^G F_N[-1-\gamma^-](x).$$

Hence, $(X, {}^G T_N[-1-\alpha^+], {}^G I_N[-1-\beta^-], {}^G F_N[-1-\gamma^-]) = {}^G X_N[-1-\alpha^+, -1-\beta^-, -1-\gamma^-]$.

2. Let ${}^G \overline{{}^G X_N[\alpha^+, \beta^+, \gamma^-]}$ be a neutrosophic $\mathcal{N}^c$ -structure over X . Then

$${}^G \overline{{}^G X_N[\alpha^+, \beta^+, \gamma^-]} = (X, {}^G \overline{{}^G T_N[\alpha^+]}, {}^G \overline{{}^G I_N[\beta^+]}, {}^G \overline{{}^G F_N[\gamma^-]}) . \text{ Since}$$

$${}^G \overline{{}^G T_N[\alpha^+]}(x) = \begin{cases} \alpha^+ & \text{if } x \in G, \\ \alpha^- & \text{otherwise,} \end{cases} \quad {}^G \overline{{}^G I_N[\beta^+]}(x) = \begin{cases} \beta^- & \text{if } x \in G, \\ \beta^+ & \text{otherwise,} \end{cases} \quad {}^G \overline{{}^G F_N[\gamma^-]}(x) = \begin{cases} \gamma^+ & \text{if } x \in G, \\ \gamma^- & \text{otherwise,} \end{cases} ,$$

we have

$${}^G \overline{{}^G T_N[\alpha^+]}(x) = \begin{cases} -1-\alpha^+ & \text{if } x \in G, \\ -1-\alpha^- & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} = T_N^G[-1-\alpha^+](x), \quad {}^G \overline{{}^G I_N[\beta^+]}(x) = \begin{cases} -1-\beta^- & \text{if } x \in G, \\ -1-\beta^+ & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} = I_N^G[-1-\beta^+](x),$$

$${}^G \overline{{}^G F_N[\gamma^-]}(x) = \begin{cases} -1-\gamma^+ & \text{if } x \in G, \\ -1-\gamma^- & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} = F_N^G[-1-\gamma^+](x).$$

Hence, $(X, T_N^G[-1-\alpha^+], I_N^G[-1-\beta^+], F_N^G[-1-\gamma^+]) = X_N^G[-1-\alpha^+, -1-\beta^+, -1-\gamma^+]$.

Lemma 5.26 If the constant 0 of X is in a nonempty subset G of X , then a neutrosophic $\mathcal{N}^c$ -structure ${}^G X_N[\alpha^+, \beta^-, \gamma^+]$ over X satisfies the conditions (5.4), (5.5), and (5.6).

Proof. If $0 \in G$, then ${}^G T_N[\alpha^+](0) = \alpha^+$, ${}^G I_N[\beta^-](0) = \beta^-$, and ${}^G F_N[\gamma^+](0) = \gamma^+$. Thus

$$(\forall x \in X) \begin{pmatrix} {}^G T_N[\alpha^+](0) = \alpha^+ \geq {}^G T_N[\alpha^+](x) \\ {}^G I_N[\beta^-](0) = \beta^- \leq {}^G I_N[\beta^-](x) \\ {}^G F_N[\gamma^+](0) = \gamma^+ \geq {}^G F_N[\gamma^+](x) \end{pmatrix}.$$

Hence, ${}^G X_N[\alpha^+, \beta^-, \gamma^+]$ satisfies the conditions (5.4), (5.5), and (5.6).

Lemma 5.27 If a neutrosophic $\mathcal{N}^c$ -structure ${}^G X_N[\alpha^+, \beta^-, \gamma^+]$ over X satisfies the condition (5.4) (resp., (5.5), (5.6)), then the constant 0 of X is in a nonempty subset G of X

Proof. Assume that a neutrosophic $\mathcal{N}^c$ -structure ${}^G X_N[\alpha^+, \beta^-, \gamma^+]$ over X satisfies the condition (5.4).

Then ${}^G T_N[\alpha^+](0) \geq {}^G T_N[\alpha^+](x)$ for all $x \in X$. Since G is nonempty, there exists $g \in G$. Thus

${}^G T_N[\alpha^+](g) = \alpha^+$, so ${}^G T_N[\alpha^+](0) \geq {}^G T_N[\alpha^+](g) = \alpha^+$, that is, ${}^G T_N[\alpha^+](0) = \alpha^+$. Hence, $0 \in G$.

Theorem 5.28 A neutrosophic $\mathcal{N}^c$ -structure ${}^G X_N[\alpha^+, \beta^-, \gamma^+]$ over X is a special neutrosophic $\mathcal{N}^c$ -UP-subalgebra of X if and only if a nonempty subset G of X is a UP-subalgebra of X .

Proof. Assume that ${}^G X_N[\alpha^+, \beta^-, \gamma^+]$ is a special neutrosophic $\mathcal{N}^c$ -UP-subalgebra of X . Let $x, y \in G$.

Then ${}^G T_N[\alpha^+](x) = \alpha^+ = {}^G T_N[\alpha^+](y)$. Thus

$${}^G T_N[\alpha^+](x \cdot y) \geq \min\{{}^G T_N[\alpha^+](x), {}^G T_N[\alpha^+](y)\} = \alpha^+ \geq {}^G T_N[\alpha^+](x \cdot y)$$

and so ${}^G T_N[\alpha^+](x \cdot y) = \alpha^+$. Thus $x \cdot y \in G$. Hence, G is a UP-subalgebra of X .

Conversely, assume that G is a UP-subalgebra of X . Let $x, y \in X$.

Case 1: $x, y \in G$. Then

$${}^G T_N[\alpha^+](x) = \alpha^+ = {}^G T_N[\alpha^+](y), \quad {}^G I_N[\beta^-](x) = \beta^- = {}^G I_N[\beta^-](y), \quad {}^G F_N[\gamma^+](x) = \gamma^+ = {}^G F_N[\gamma^+](y).$$

Thus

$$\min\{{}^G T_N[\alpha^+](x), {}^G T_N[\alpha^+](y)\} = \alpha^+, \quad \max\{{}^G I_N[\beta^-](x), {}^G I_N[\beta^-](y)\} = \beta^-, \quad \min\{{}^G F_N[\gamma^+](x), {}^G F_N[\gamma^+](y)\} = \gamma^+.$$

Since G is a UP-subalgebra of X , we have $x \cdot y \in G$ and so ${}^G T_N[\alpha^-](x \cdot y) = \alpha^+$, ${}^G I_N[\beta^+](x \cdot y) = \beta^-$, and ${}^G F_N[\gamma^-](x \cdot y) = \gamma^+$. Hence,

$${}^G T_N[\alpha^-](x \cdot y) = \alpha^+ \geq \alpha^+ = \min\{{}^G T_N[\alpha^-](x), {}^G T_N[\alpha^-](y)\},$$

$${}^G I_N[\beta^+](x \cdot y) = \beta^- \leq \beta^- = \max\{{}^G I_N[\beta^+](x), {}^G I_N[\beta^+](y)\},$$

$${}^G F_N[\gamma^-](x \cdot y) = \gamma^+ \geq \gamma^+ = \min\{{}^G F_N[\gamma^-](x), {}^G F_N[\gamma^-](y)\}.$$

Case 2: $x \notin G$ or $y \notin G$. Then

$${}^G T_N[\alpha^-](x) = \alpha^- \text{ or } {}^G T_N[\alpha^-](y) = \alpha^-, \quad {}^G I_N[\beta^+](x) = \beta^+ \text{ or } {}^G I_N[\beta^+](y) = \beta^+,$$

$${}^G F_N[\gamma^-](x) = \gamma^- \text{ or } {}^G F_N[\gamma^-](y) = \gamma^-.$$

Thus

$$\min\{{}^G T_N[\alpha^-](x), {}^G T_N[\alpha^-](y)\} = \alpha^-, \quad \max\{{}^G I_N[\beta^+](x), {}^G I_N[\beta^+](y)\} = \beta^+, \quad \min\{{}^G F_N[\gamma^-](x), {}^G F_N[\gamma^-](y)\} = \gamma^-.$$

Therefore,

$${}^G T_N[\alpha^-](x \cdot y) \geq \alpha^- = \min\{{}^G T_N[\alpha^-](x), {}^G T_N[\alpha^-](y)\},$$

$${}^G I_N[\beta^+](x \cdot y) \leq \beta^+ = \max\{{}^G I_N[\beta^+](x), {}^G I_N[\beta^+](y)\},$$

$${}^G F_N[\gamma^-](x \cdot y) \geq \gamma^- = \min\{{}^G F_N[\gamma^-](x), {}^G F_N[\gamma^-](y)\}.$$

Hence, ${}^G X_N[\alpha^-, \beta^+, \gamma^-]$ is a special neutrosophic $\mathcal{N}$ -UP-subalgebra of X .

Theorem 5.29 A neutrosophic $\mathcal{N}$ -structure ${}^G X_N[\alpha^-, \beta^+, \gamma^-]$ over X is a special neutrosophic $\mathcal{N}$ -near UP-filter of X if and only if a nonempty subset G of X is a near UP-filter of X .

Proof. Assume that ${}^G X_N[\alpha^-, \beta^+, \gamma^-]$ is a special neutrosophic $\mathcal{N}$ -near UP-filter of X . Since

${}^G X_N[\alpha^-, \beta^+, \gamma^-]$ satisfies the condition (5.4), it follows from Lemma 5.27 that $0 \in G$. Next, let $x \in X$

and $y \in G$. Then ${}^G T_N[\alpha^-](y) = \alpha^+$. Thus, by (5.7), we have

$${}^G T_N[\alpha^-](x \cdot y) \geq {}^G T_N[\alpha^-](y) = \alpha^+ \geq {}^G T_N[\alpha^-](x \cdot y)$$

and so ${}^G T_N[\alpha^-](x \cdot y) = \alpha^+$. Thus $x \cdot y \in G$. Hence, G is a near UP-filter of X .

Conversely, assume that G is a near UP-filter of X . Since $0 \in G$, it follows from Lemma 5.26 that ${}^G X_N[\alpha^+, \beta^-, \gamma^+]$ satisfies the conditions (5.4), (5.5), and (5.6). Next, let $x, y \in X$.

Case 1: $y \in G$. Then ${}^G T_N[\alpha^+](y) = \alpha^+$, ${}^G I_N[\beta^-](y) = \beta^-$, and ${}^G F_N[\gamma^-](y) = \gamma^-$. Since G is a near UP-filter of X , we have $x \cdot y \in G$ and so ${}^G T_N[\alpha^+](x \cdot y) = \alpha^+$, ${}^G I_N[\beta^-](x \cdot y) = \beta^-$, and ${}^G F_N[\gamma^-](x \cdot y) = \gamma^-$. Thus

$${}^G T_N[\alpha^+](x \cdot y) = \alpha^+ \geq \alpha^+ = {}^G T_N[\alpha^+](y), \quad {}^G I_N[\beta^-](x \cdot y) = \beta^- \leq \beta^- = {}^G I_N[\beta^-](y),$$

$${}^G F_N[\gamma^-](x \cdot y) = \gamma^- \geq \gamma^- = {}^G F_N[\gamma^-](y).$$

Case 2: $y \notin G$. Then ${}^G T_N[\alpha^+](y) = \alpha^-$, ${}^G I_N[\beta^-](y) = \beta^+$, and ${}^G F_N[\gamma^-](y) = \gamma^+$. Thus

$${}^G T_N[\alpha^+](x \cdot y) \geq \alpha^- = {}^G T_N[\alpha^+](y), \quad {}^G I_N[\beta^-](x \cdot y) \leq \beta^+ = {}^G I_N[\beta^-](y), \quad {}^G F_N[\gamma^-](x \cdot y) \geq \gamma^+ = {}^G F_N[\gamma^-](y).$$

Hence, ${}^G X_N[\alpha^+, \beta^-, \gamma^+]$ is a special neutrosophic $\mathcal{N}^c$ -near UP-filter of X .

Theorem 5.30 A neutrosophic $\mathcal{N}^c$ -structure ${}^G X_N[\alpha^+, \beta^-, \gamma^+]$ over X is a special neutrosophic $\mathcal{N}^c$ -UP-filter of X if and only if a nonempty subset G of X is a UP-filter of X .

Proof. Assume that ${}^G X_N[\alpha^+, \beta^-, \gamma^+]$ is a special neutrosophic $\mathcal{N}^c$ -UP-filter of X . Since ${}^G X_N[\alpha^+, \beta^-, \gamma^+]$ satisfies the condition (5.4), it follows from Lemma 5.27 that $0 \in G$. Next, let $x, y \in X$ be such that $x \cdot y \in G$ and $x \in G$. Then ${}^G T_N[\alpha^+](x \cdot y) = \alpha^+ = {}^G T_N[\alpha^+](x)$. Thus, by (5.10), we have

$${}^G T_N[\alpha^+](y) \geq \min\{{}^G T_N[\alpha^+](x \cdot y), {}^G T_N[\alpha^+](x)\} = \alpha^+ \geq {}^G T_N[\alpha^+](y)$$

and so ${}^G T_N[\alpha^+](y) = \alpha^+$. Thus $y \in G$. Hence, G is a UP-filter of X .

Conversely, assume that G is a UP-filter of X . Since $0 \in G$, it follows from Lemma 5.26 that ${}^G X_N[\alpha^+, \beta^-, \gamma^+]$ satisfies the conditions (5.4), (5.5), and (5.6). Next, let $x, y \in X$.

Case 1: $x \cdot y \in G$ and $x \in G$. Then

$${}^G T_N[\alpha^+](x \cdot y) = \alpha^+ = {}^G T_N[\alpha^+](x), \quad {}^G I_N[\beta^-](x \cdot y) = \beta^- = {}^G I_N[\beta^-](x), \quad {}^G F_N[\gamma^-](x \cdot y) = \gamma^- = {}^G F_N[\gamma^-](x).$$

Since G is a UP-filter of X , we have $y \in G$ and so ${}^G T_N[\alpha^+](y) = \alpha^+$, ${}^G I_N[\beta^-](y) = \beta^-$, and

${}^G F_N[\gamma^-](y) = \gamma^-$. Thus

$${}^G T_N[\alpha^-]^\alpha(y) = \alpha^+ \geq \alpha^+ = \min\{{}^G T_N[\alpha^-]^\alpha(x \cdot y), {}^G T_N[\alpha^-]^\alpha(x)\},$$

$${}^G I_N[\beta^+]^\beta(y) = \beta^- \leq \beta^- = \max\{{}^G I_N[\beta^+]^\beta(x \cdot y), {}^G I_N[\beta^+]^\beta(x)\},$$

$${}^G F_N[\gamma^-]^\gamma(y) = \gamma^+ \geq \gamma^+ = \min\{{}^G F_N[\gamma^-]^\gamma(x \cdot y), {}^G F_N[\gamma^-]^\gamma(x)\}.$$

Case 2: $x \cdot y \notin G$ or $x \notin G$. Then

$${}^G T_N[\alpha^-]^\alpha(x \cdot y) = \alpha^- \text{ or } {}^G T_N[\alpha^-]^\alpha(x) = \alpha^-, \quad {}^G I_N[\beta^+]^\beta(x \cdot y) = \beta^+ \text{ or } {}^G I_N[\beta^+]^\beta(x) = \beta^+,$$

$${}^G F_N[\gamma^-]^\gamma(x \cdot y) = \gamma^- \text{ or } {}^G F_N[\gamma^-]^\gamma(x) = \gamma^-.$$

Thus

$$\min\{{}^G T_N[\alpha^-]^\alpha(x \cdot y), {}^G T_N[\alpha^-]^\alpha(x)\} = \alpha^-, \quad \max\{{}^G I_N[\beta^+]^\beta(x \cdot y), {}^G I_N[\beta^+]^\beta(x)\} = \beta^+,$$

$$\min\{{}^G F_N[\gamma^-]^\gamma(x \cdot y), {}^G F_N[\gamma^-]^\gamma(x)\} = \gamma^-.$$

Therefore,

$${}^G T_N[\alpha^-]^\alpha(x) \geq \alpha^- = \min\{{}^G T_N[\alpha^-]^\alpha(x \cdot y), {}^G T_N[\alpha^-]^\alpha(x)\},$$

$${}^G I_N[\beta^+]^\beta(x) \leq \beta^+ = \max\{{}^G I_N[\beta^+]^\beta(x \cdot y), {}^G I_N[\beta^+]^\beta(x)\},$$

$${}^G F_N[\gamma^-]^\gamma(x) \geq \gamma^- = \min\{{}^G F_N[\gamma^-]^\gamma(x \cdot y), {}^G F_N[\gamma^-]^\gamma(x)\}.$$

Hence, ${}^G X_N[\alpha^-, \beta^+, \gamma^-]^{\alpha^+, \beta^-, \gamma^+}$ is a special neutrosophic $\mathcal{N}^c$ -UP-filter of X .

Theorem 5.31 A neutrosophic $\mathcal{N}^c$ -structure ${}^G X_N[\alpha^-, \beta^+, \gamma^-]^{\alpha^+, \beta^-, \gamma^+}$ over X is a special neutrosophic $\mathcal{N}^c$ -UP-ideal of X if and only if a nonempty subset G of X is a UP-ideal of X .

Proof. Assume that ${}^G X_N[\alpha^-, \beta^+, \gamma^-]^{\alpha^+, \beta^-, \gamma^+}$ is a special neutrosophic $\mathcal{N}^c$ -UP-ideal of X . Since ${}^G X_N[\alpha^-, \beta^+, \gamma^-]^{\alpha^+, \beta^-, \gamma^+}$ satisfies the condition (5.4), it follows from Lemma 5.27, that $0 \in G$. Next, let $x, y, z \in X$ be such that $x \cdot (y \cdot z) \in G$ and $y \in G$. Then ${}^G T_N[\alpha^-]^\alpha(x \cdot (y \cdot z)) = \alpha^+ = {}^G T_N[\alpha^-]^\alpha(y)$. Thus, by (5.13), we have

$${}^G T_N[\alpha^-]^\alpha(x \cdot z) \geq \min\{{}^G T_N[\alpha^-]^\alpha(x \cdot (y \cdot z)), {}^G T_N[\alpha^-]^\alpha(y)\} = \alpha^+ \geq {}^G T_N[\alpha^-]^\alpha(x \cdot z)$$

and so ${}^G T_N[\alpha^-]^\alpha(x \cdot z) = \alpha^+$. Thus $x \cdot z \in G$. Hence, G is a UP-ideal of X .

Conversely, assume that G is a UP-ideal of X . Since $0 \in G$, it follows from Lemma 5.26 that ${}^G X_N[\alpha^-, \beta^+, \gamma^-]^{\alpha^+, \beta^-, \gamma^+}$ satisfies the conditions (5.4), (5.5), and (5.6). Next, let $x, y, z \in X$.

Case 1: $x \cdot (y \cdot z) \in G$ and $y \in G$. Then

$$\begin{aligned}
 {}^G T_N[\alpha^-](x \cdot (y \cdot z)) &= \alpha^+ = {}^G T_N[\alpha^-](y), & {}^G I_N[\beta^+](x \cdot (y \cdot z)) &= \beta^- = {}^G I_N[\beta^+](y), \\
 {}^G F_N[\gamma^-](x \cdot (y \cdot z)) &= \gamma^+ = {}^G F_N[\gamma^-](y).
 \end{aligned}$$

Thus

$$\begin{aligned}
 \min\{{}^G T_N[\alpha^-](x \cdot (y \cdot z)), {}^G T_N[\alpha^-](y)\} &= \alpha^+, & \max\{{}^G I_N[\beta^+](x \cdot (y \cdot z)), {}^G I_N[\beta^+](y)\} &= \beta^-, \\
 \min\{{}^G F_N[\gamma^-](x \cdot (y \cdot z)), {}^G F_N[\gamma^-](y)\} &= \gamma^+.
 \end{aligned}$$

Since G is a UP-ideal of X , we have $x \cdot z \in G$ and so ${}^G T_N[\alpha^-](x \cdot z) = \alpha^+$, ${}^G I_N[\beta^+](x \cdot z) = \beta^-$, and

${}^G F_N[\gamma^-](x \cdot z) = \gamma^+$. Thus

$$\begin{aligned}
 {}^G T_N[\alpha^-](x \cdot z) &= \alpha^+ \geq \alpha^+ = \min\{{}^G T_N[\alpha^-](x \cdot (y \cdot z)), {}^G T_N[\alpha^-](y)\}, \\
 {}^G I_N[\beta^+](x \cdot z) &= \beta^- \leq \beta^- = \max\{{}^G I_N[\beta^+](x \cdot (y \cdot z)), {}^G I_N[\beta^+](y)\}, \\
 {}^G F_N[\gamma^-](x \cdot z) &= \gamma^+ \geq \gamma^+ = \min\{{}^G F_N[\gamma^-](x \cdot (y \cdot z)), {}^G F_N[\gamma^-](y)\}.
 \end{aligned}$$

Case 2: $x \cdot (y \cdot z) \notin G$ or $y \notin G$. Then

$$\begin{aligned}
 {}^G T_N[\alpha^-](x \cdot (y \cdot z)) &= \alpha^- \text{ or } {}^G T_N[\alpha^-](y) = \alpha^-, & {}^G I_N[\beta^+](x \cdot (y \cdot z)) &= \beta^+ \text{ or } {}^G I_N[\beta^+](y) = \beta^+, \\
 {}^G F_N[\gamma^-](x \cdot (y \cdot z)) &= \gamma^- \text{ or } {}^G F_N[\gamma^-](y) = \gamma^-.
 \end{aligned}$$

Thus

$$\begin{aligned}
 \min\{{}^G T_N[\alpha^-](x \cdot (y \cdot z)), {}^G T_N[\alpha^-](y)\} &= \alpha^-, & \max\{{}^G I_N[\beta^+](x \cdot (y \cdot z)), {}^G I_N[\beta^+](y)\} &= \beta^+, \\
 \min\{{}^G F_N[\gamma^-](x \cdot (y \cdot z)), {}^G F_N[\gamma^-](y)\} &= \gamma^-.
 \end{aligned}$$

Therefore,

$$\begin{aligned}
 {}^G T_N[\alpha^-](x \cdot z) &\geq \alpha^- = \min\{{}^G T_N[\alpha^-](x \cdot (y \cdot z)), {}^G T_N[\alpha^-](y)\}, \\
 {}^G I_N[\beta^+](x \cdot z) &\leq \beta^+ = \max\{{}^G I_N[\beta^+](x \cdot (y \cdot z)), {}^G I_N[\beta^+](y)\}, \\
 {}^G F_N[\gamma^-](x \cdot z) &\geq \gamma^- = \min\{{}^G F_N[\gamma^-](x \cdot (y \cdot z)), {}^G F_N[\gamma^-](y)\}.
 \end{aligned}$$

Hence, ${}^G X_N[\alpha^-, \beta^+, \gamma^-]$ is a special neutrosophic $\mathcal{N}^c$ -UP-ideal of X .

Theorem 5.32 A neutrosophic $\mathcal{N}^c$ -structure ${}^G X_N[\alpha^+, \beta^-, \gamma^+]$ over X is a special neutrosophic $\mathcal{N}^c$ -strongly UP-ideal of X if and only if a nonempty subset G of X is a strongly UP-ideal of X .

Proof. Assume that ${}^G X_N[\alpha^+, \beta^-, \gamma^+]$ is a special neutrosophic $\mathcal{N}$ -strongly UP-ideal of X . By Theorem 5.17, we have ${}^G T_N[\alpha^+]$ is constant, that is, ${}^G T_N[\alpha^+]$ is constant. Since G is nonempty, we have ${}^G T_N[\alpha^+](x) = \alpha^+$ for all $x \in X$. Thus $G = X$. Hence, G is a strongly UP-ideal of X .

Conversely, assume that G is a strongly UP-ideal of X . Then $G = X$, so

$$(\forall x \in X) \begin{pmatrix} {}^G T_N[\alpha^+](x) = \alpha^+ \\ {}^G I_N[\beta^+](x) = \beta^- \\ {}^G F_N[\gamma^+](x) = \gamma^+ \end{pmatrix}.$$

Thus ${}^G T_N[\alpha^+]$, ${}^G I_N[\beta^+]$, and ${}^G F_N[\gamma^+]$ are constant, that is, ${}^G X_N[\alpha^+, \beta^-, \gamma^+]$ is constant. By Theorem 5.17, we have ${}^G X_N[\alpha^+, \beta^-, \gamma^+]$ is a special neutrosophic $\mathcal{N}$ -strongly UP-ideal of X .

6. Level subset of a neutrosophic $\mathcal{N}$ -structure of special type

In the last section of this paper, we discuss the relationships among special neutrosophic $\mathcal{N}$ -UP-subalgebras (resp., special neutrosophic $\mathcal{N}$ -near UP-filters, special neutrosophic $\mathcal{N}$ -UP-filters, special neutrosophic $\mathcal{N}$ -UP-ideals, special neutrosophic $\mathcal{N}$ -strongly UP-ideals) of UP-algebras and their level subsets.

Theorem 6.1 A neutrosophic $\mathcal{N}$ -structure X_N over X is a special neutrosophic $\mathcal{N}$ -UP-subalgebra of X if and only if for all $\alpha, \beta, \gamma \in [-1, 0]$, the sets $U(T_N; \alpha), L(I_N; \beta)$, and $U(F_N; \gamma)$ are UP-subalgebras of X if $U(T_N; \alpha), L(I_N; \beta)$, and $U(F_N; \gamma)$ are nonempty.

Proof. Assume that X_N is a special neutrosophic $\mathcal{N}$ -UP-subalgebra of X . Let $\alpha, \beta, \gamma \in [-1, 0]$ be such that $U(T_N; \alpha), L(I_N; \beta)$, and $U(F_N; \gamma)$ are nonempty.

Let $x, y \in U(T_N; \alpha)$. Then $T_N(x) \geq \alpha$ and $T_N(y) \geq \alpha$, so α is a lower bound of $\{T_N(x), T_N(y)\}$. By (5.1), we have $T_N(x \cdot y) \geq \min\{T_N(x), T_N(y)\} \geq \alpha$. Thus $x \cdot y \in U(T_N; \alpha)$.

Let $x, y \in L(I_N; \beta)$. Then $I_N(x) \leq \beta$ and $I_N(y) \leq \beta$, so β is an upper bound of $\{I_N(x), I_N(y)\}$. By (5.2), we have $I_N(x \cdot y) \leq \max\{I_N(x), I_N(y)\} \leq \beta$. Thus $x \cdot y \in L(I_N; \beta)$.

Let $x, y \in U(F_N; \gamma)$. Then $F_N(x) \geq \gamma$ and $F_N(y) \geq \gamma$, so γ is a lower bound of $\{F_N(x), F_N(y)\}$. By (5.3), we have $F_N(x \cdot y) \geq \min\{F_N(x), F_N(y)\} \geq \gamma$. Thus $x \cdot y \in U(F_N; \gamma)$.

Hence, $U(T_N; \alpha), L(I_N; \beta)$, and $U(F_N; \gamma)$ are UP-subalgebras of X .

Conversely, assume that for all $\alpha, \beta, \gamma \in [-1, 0]$, the set $U(T_N; \alpha), L(I_N; \beta)$, and $U(F_N; \gamma)$ are UP-subalgebras if $U(T_N; \alpha), L(I_N; \beta)$, and $U(F_N; \gamma)$ are nonempty.

Let $x, y \in X$. Then $T_N(x), T_N(y) \in [-1, 0]$. Choose $\alpha = \min\{T_N(x), T_N(y)\}$. Thus $T_N(x) \geq \alpha$ and $T_N(y) \geq \alpha$, so $x, y \in U(T_N; \alpha) \neq \emptyset$. By assumption, we have $U(T_N; \alpha)$ is a UP-subalgebra of X and so $x, y \in U(T_N; \alpha)$. Thus $T_N(x \cdot y) \geq \alpha = \min\{T_N(x), T_N(y)\}$.

Let $x, y \in X$. Then $I_N(x), I_N(y) \in [-1, 0]$. Choose $\beta = \max\{I_N(x), I_N(y)\}$. Thus $I_N(x) \leq \beta$ and $I_N(y) \leq \beta$, so $x, y \in L(I_N; \beta) \neq \emptyset$. By assumption, we have $L(I_N; \beta)$ is a UP-subalgebra of X and so $x, y \in L(I_N; \beta)$. Thus $I_N(x \cdot y) \leq \beta = \max\{I_N(x), I_N(y)\}$.

Let $x, y \in X$. Then $F_N(x), F_N(y) \in [-1, 0]$. Choose $\gamma = \min\{F_N(x), F_N(y)\}$. Thus $F_N(x) \geq \gamma$ and $F_N(y) \geq \gamma$, so $x, y \in U(F_N; \gamma) \neq \emptyset$. By assumption, we have $U(F_N; \gamma)$ is a UP-subalgebra of X and so $x, y \in U(F_N; \gamma)$. Thus $F_N(x \cdot y) \leq \gamma = \min\{F_N(x), F_N(y)\}$.

Therefore, X_N is a special neutrosophic $\mathcal{N}^c$ -UP-subalgebra of X .

Theorem 6.2 A neutrosophic $\mathcal{N}^c$ -structure X_N over X is a special neutrosophic $\mathcal{N}^c$ -near UP-filter of X if and only if for all $\alpha, \beta, \gamma \in [-1, 0]$, the sets $U(T_N; \alpha), L(I_N; \beta)$, and $U(F_N; \gamma)$ are near UP-filters of X if $U(T_N; \alpha), L(I_N; \beta)$, and $U(F_N; \gamma)$ are nonempty.

Proof. Assume that X_N is a special neutrosophic $\mathcal{N}^c$ -near UP-filter of X . Let $\alpha, \beta, \gamma \in [-1, 0]$ be such that $U(T_N; \alpha), L(I_N; \beta)$, and $U(F_N; \gamma)$ are nonempty.

Let $x \in U(T_N; \alpha)$. Then $T_N(x) \geq \alpha$. By (5.4), we have $T_N(0) \geq T_N(x) \geq \alpha$. Thus $0 \in U(T_N; \alpha)$. Next, let $y \in U(T_N; \alpha)$. Then $T_N(y) \geq \alpha$. By (5.7), we have $T_N(x \cdot y) \geq T_N(y) \geq \alpha$. Thus $x \cdot y \in U(T_N; \alpha)$.

Let $x \in L(I_N; \beta)$. Then $I_N(x) \leq \beta$. By (5.5), we have $I_N(0) \leq I_N(x) \leq \beta$. Thus $0 \in L(I_N; \beta)$. Next, let $y \in L(I_N; \beta)$. Then $I_N(y) \leq \beta$. By (5.8), we have $I_N(x \cdot y) \leq I_N(y) \leq \beta$. Thus $x \cdot y \in L(I_N; \beta)$.

Let $x \in U(F_N; \gamma)$. Then $F_N(x) \geq \gamma$. By (5.6), we have $F_N(0) \geq F_N(x) \geq \gamma$. Thus $0 \in U(F_N; \gamma)$. Next, let $y \in U(F_N; \gamma)$. Then $F_N(y) \geq \gamma$. By (5.9), we have $F_N(x \cdot y) \geq F_N(y) \geq \gamma$. Thus $x \cdot y \in U(F_N; \gamma)$.

Hence, $U(T_N; \alpha), L(I_N; \beta)$, and $U(F_N; \gamma)$ are near UP-filters of X .

Conversely, assume that for all $\alpha, \beta, \gamma \in [-1, 0]$, the set $U(T_N; \alpha), L(I_N; \beta)$, and $U(F_N; \gamma)$ are near UP-filters if $U(T_N; \alpha), L(I_N; \beta)$, and $U(F_N; \gamma)$ are nonempty.

Let $x \in X$. Then $T_N(0) \in [-1, 0]$. Choose $\alpha = T_N(x)$. Thus $T_N(x) \geq \alpha$, so $x \in L(T_N; \alpha) \neq \emptyset$. By assumption, we have $U(T_N; \alpha)$ is a near UP-filter of X and so $0 \in U(T_N; \alpha)$. Thus $T_N(0) \geq \alpha = T_N(x)$. Next, let $y \in X$. Then $T_N(y) \in [-1, 0]$. Choose $\alpha = T_N(y)$. Thus $T_N(y) \geq \alpha$, so $y \in U(T_N; \alpha) \neq \emptyset$. By assumption, we have $U(T_N; \alpha)$ is a near UP-filter of X , and so $x \cdot y \in U(T_N; \alpha)$. Thus $T_N(x \cdot y) \geq \alpha = T_N(y)$.

Let $x \in X$. Then $I_N(0) \in [-1, 0]$. Choose $\beta = I_N(x)$. Thus $I_N(x) \leq \beta$, so $x \in L(I_N; \beta) \neq \emptyset$. By assumption, we have $L(I_N; \beta)$ is a near UP-filter of X and so $0 \in L(I_N; \beta)$. Thus $I_N(0) \leq \beta = I_N(x)$. Next, let $y \in X$. Then $I_N(y) \in [-1, 0]$. Choose $\beta = I_N(y)$. Thus $I_N(y) \leq \beta$, so $y \in L(I_N; \beta) \neq \emptyset$. By assumption, we have $L(I_N; \beta)$ is a near UP-filter of X , and so $x \cdot y \in L(I_N; \beta)$. Thus $I_N(x \cdot y) \leq \beta = I_N(y)$.

Let $x \in X$. Then $F_N(0) \in [-1, 0]$. Choose $\gamma = F_N(x)$. Thus $F_N(x) \geq \gamma$, so $x \in U(F_N; \gamma) \neq \emptyset$. By assumption, we have $U(F_N; \gamma)$ is a near UP-filter of X and so $0 \in U(F_N; \gamma)$. Thus $F_N(0) \geq \gamma = F_N(x)$. Next, let $y \in X$. Then $F_N(y) \in [-1, 0]$. Choose $\gamma = F_N(y)$. Thus $F_N(y) \geq \gamma$, so $y \in U(F_N; \gamma) \neq \emptyset$. By assumption, we have $U(F_N; \gamma)$ is a near UP-filter of X , and so $x \cdot y \in U(F_N; \gamma)$. Thus $F_N(x \cdot y) \geq \gamma = F_N(y)$.

Therefore, X_N is a special neutrosophic $\mathcal{N}^c$ -near UP-filter of X .

Theorem 6.3 A neutrosophic $\mathcal{N}^c$ -structure X_N over X is a special neutrosophic $\mathcal{N}^c$ -UP-filter of X if and only if for all $\alpha, \beta, \gamma \in [-1, 0]$, the sets $U(T_N; \alpha), L(I_N; \beta)$, and $U(F_N; \gamma)$ are UP-filters of X if $U(T_N; \alpha), L(I_N; \beta)$, and $U(F_N; \gamma)$ are nonempty.

Proof. Assume that X_N is a special neutrosophic $\mathcal{N}^c$ -UP-filter of X . Let $\alpha, \beta, \gamma \in [-1, 0]$ be such that $U(T_N; \alpha), L(I_N; \beta)$, and $U(F_N; \gamma)$ are nonempty.

Let $x \in U(T_N; \alpha)$. Then $T_N(x) \geq \alpha$. By (5.4), we have $T_N(0) \geq T_N(x) \geq \alpha$. Thus $0 \in U(T_N; \alpha)$. Next, let $x \cdot y \in U(T_N; \alpha)$ and $x \in U(T_N; \alpha)$. Then $T_N(x \cdot y) \geq \alpha$ and $T_N(x) \leq \alpha$, so α is a lower bound of $\{T_N(x \cdot y), T_N(x)\}$. By (5.10), we have $T_N(y) \geq \min\{T_N(x \cdot y), T_N(x)\} \geq \alpha$. Thus $y \in U(T_N; \alpha)$.

Let $x \in L(I_N; \beta)$. Then $I_N(x) \leq \beta$. By (5.5), we have $I_N(0) \leq I_N(x) \leq \beta$. Thus $0 \in L(I_N; \beta)$. Next, let $x \cdot y \in L(I_N; \beta)$ and $x \in L(I_N; \beta)$. Then $I_N(x \cdot y) \leq \beta$ and $I_N(x) \leq \beta$, so β is an upper bound of $\{I_N(x \cdot y), I_N(x)\}$. By (5.11), we have $I_N(y) \leq \max\{I_N(x \cdot y), I_N(x)\} \leq \beta$. Thus $y \in L(I_N; \beta)$.

Let $x \in U(F_N; \gamma)$. Then $F_N(x) \geq \gamma$. By (5.6), we have $F_N(0) \geq F_N(x) \geq \gamma$. Thus $0 \in U(F_N; \gamma)$. Next, let $x \cdot y \in U(F_N; \gamma)$ and $x \in U(F_N; \gamma)$. Then $F_N(x \cdot y) \geq \gamma$ and $F_N(x) \geq \gamma$, so γ is a lower bound of $\{F_N(x \cdot y), F_N(x)\}$. By (5.12), we have $F_N(y) \geq \min\{F_N(x \cdot y), F_N(x)\} \geq \gamma$. Thus $y \in U(F_N; \gamma)$.

Hence, $U(T_N; \alpha), L(I_N; \beta)$, and $U(F_N; \gamma)$ are UP-filters of X .

Conversely, assume that for all $\alpha, \beta, \gamma \in [-1, 0]$, the set $U(T_N; \alpha), L(I_N; \beta)$, and $U(F_N; \gamma)$ are UP-filters if $U(T_N; \alpha), L(I_N; \beta)$, and $U(F_N; \gamma)$ are nonempty.

Let $x \in X$. Then $T_N(x) \in [-1, 0]$. Choose $\alpha = T_N(x)$. Thus $T_N(x) \geq \alpha$, so $x \in U(T_N; \alpha) \neq \emptyset$. By assumption, we have $U(T_N; \alpha)$ is a UP-filter of X and so $0 \in U(T_N; \alpha)$. Thus $T_N(0) \geq \alpha = T_N(x)$. Next, let $x, y \in X$. Then $T_N(x \cdot y), T_N(x) \in [-1, 0]$. Choose $\alpha = \min\{T_N(x \cdot y), T_N(x)\}$. Thus $T_N(x \cdot y) \geq \alpha$ and $T_N(x) \geq \alpha$, so $x \cdot y, x \in U(T_N; \alpha) \neq \emptyset$. By assumption, we have $U(T_N; \alpha)$ is a UP-filter of X and so $y \in U(T_N; \alpha)$. Thus $T_N(y) \geq \alpha = \min\{T_N(x \cdot y), T_N(x)\}$.

Let $x \in X$. Then $I_N(x) \in [-1, 0]$. Choose $\beta = I_N(x)$. Thus $I_N(x) \leq \beta$, so $x \in L(I_N; \beta) \neq \emptyset$. By assumption, we have $L(I_N; \beta)$ is a UP-filter of X and so $0 \in L(I_N; \beta)$. Thus $I_N(0) \leq \beta = I_N(x)$. Next, let $x, y \in X$. Then $I_N(x \cdot y), I_N(x) \in [-1, 0]$. Choose $\beta = \max\{I_N(x \cdot y), I_N(x)\}$. Thus $I_N(x \cdot y) \leq \beta$ and $I_N(x) \leq \beta$, so $x \cdot y, x \in L(I_N; \beta) \neq \emptyset$. By assumption, we have $L(I_N; \beta)$ is a UP-filter of X and so $y \in L(I_N; \beta)$. Thus $I_N(y) \leq \beta = \max\{I_N(x \cdot y), I_N(x)\}$.

Let $x \in X$. Then $F_N(x) \in [-1, 0]$. Choose $\gamma = F_N(x)$. Thus $F_N(x) \leq \gamma$, so $x \in U(F_N; \gamma) \neq \emptyset$. By assumption, we have $U(F_N; \gamma)$ is a UP-filter of X and so $0 \in U(F_N; \gamma)$. Thus $F_N(0) \geq \gamma = F_N(x)$. Next, let $x, y \in X$. Then $F_N(x \cdot y), F_N(x) \in [-1, 0]$. Choose $\gamma = \min\{F_N(x \cdot y), F_N(x)\}$. Thus $F_N(x \cdot y) \geq \gamma$ and $F_N(x) \geq \gamma$, so $x \cdot y, x \in U(F_N; \gamma) \neq \emptyset$. By assumption, we have $U(F_N; \gamma)$ is a UP-filter of X and so $y \in U(F_N; \gamma)$. Thus $F_N(y) \geq \gamma = \min\{F_N(x \cdot y), F_N(x)\}$.

Therefore, X_N is a special neutrosophic $\mathcal{N}^c$ -UP-filter of X .

Theorem 6.4 A neutrosophic $\mathcal{N}^c$ -structure X_N over X is a special neutrosophic $\mathcal{N}^c$ -UP-ideals of X if and only if for all $\alpha, \beta, \gamma \in [-1, 0]$, the sets $U(T_N; \alpha), L(I_N; \beta)$, and $U(F_N; \gamma)$ are UP-ideals of X if $U(T_N; \alpha), L(I_N; \beta)$, and $U(F_N; \gamma)$ are nonempty.

Proof. Assume that X_N is a special neutrosophic $\mathcal{N}^c$ -UP-ideal of X . Let $\alpha, \beta, \gamma \in [-1, 0]$ be such that $U(T_N; \alpha), L(I_N; \beta)$, and $U(F_N; \gamma)$ are nonempty.

Let $x \in U(T_N; \alpha)$. Then $T_N(x) \geq \alpha$. By (5.4), we have $T_N(0) \geq T_N(x) \geq \alpha$. Thus $0 \in U(T_N; \alpha)$. Next, let $x \cdot (y \cdot z) \in U(T_N; \alpha)$ and $y \in U(T_N; \alpha)$. Then $T_N(x \cdot (y \cdot z)) \geq \alpha$ and $T_N(y) \geq \alpha$, so α is a

lower bound of $\{T_N(x \cdot (y \cdot z)), T_N(y)\}$. By (5.13), we have $T_N(x \cdot z) \geq \min\{T_N(x \cdot (y \cdot z)), T_N(y)\} \geq \alpha$. Thus $x \cdot z \in U(T_N; \alpha)$.

Let $x \in L(I_N; \beta)$. Then $I_N(x) \leq \beta$. By (5.5), we have $I_N(0) \leq I_N(x) \leq \beta$. Thus $0 \in L(I_N; \beta)$. Next, let $x \cdot (y \cdot z) \in L(I_N; \beta)$ and $y \in L(I_N; \beta)$. Then $I_N(x \cdot (y \cdot z)) \leq \beta$ and $I_N(y) \leq \beta$, so β is an upper bound of $\{I_N(x \cdot (y \cdot z)), I_N(y)\}$. By (5.14), we have $I_N(x \cdot z) \leq \max\{I_N(x \cdot (y \cdot z)), I_N(y)\} \leq \beta$. Thus $x \cdot z \in L(I_N; \beta)$.

Let $x \in U(F_N; \gamma)$. Then $F_N(x) \geq \gamma$. By (5.6), we have $F_N(0) \geq F_N(x) \geq \gamma$. Thus $0 \in U(F_N; \gamma)$. Next, let $x \cdot (y \cdot z) \in U(F_N; \gamma)$ and $y \in U(F_N; \gamma)$. Then $F_N(x \cdot (y \cdot z)) \geq \gamma$ and $F_N(y) \geq \gamma$, so γ is a lower bound of $\{F_N(x \cdot (y \cdot z)), F_N(y)\}$. By (5.15), we have $F_N(x \cdot z) \geq \min\{F_N(x \cdot (y \cdot z)), F_N(y)\} \geq \gamma$. Thus $x \cdot z \in U(F_N; \gamma)$.

Hence, $U(T_N; \alpha), L(I_N; \beta)$, and $U(F_N; \gamma)$ are UP-ideals of X .

Conversely, assume that for all $\alpha, \beta, \gamma \in [-1, 0]$, the set $U(T_N; \alpha), L(I_N; \beta)$, and $U(F_N; \gamma)$ are UP-ideals if $U(T_N; \alpha), L(I_N; \beta)$, and $U(F_N; \gamma)$ are nonempty.

Let $x \in X$. Then $T_N(x) \in [-1, 0]$. Choose $\alpha = T_N(x)$. Thus $T_N(x) \geq \alpha$, so $x \in U(T_N; \alpha) \neq \emptyset$. By assumption, we have $U(T_N; \alpha)$ is a UP-ideal of X and so $0 \in U(T_N; \alpha)$. Thus $T_N(0) \geq \alpha = T_N(x)$. Next, let $x, y, z \in X$. Then $T_N(x \cdot (y \cdot z)), T_N(y) \in [-1, 0]$. Choose $\alpha = \min\{T_N(x \cdot (y \cdot z)), T_N(y)\}$. Thus $T_N(x \cdot (y \cdot z)) \geq \alpha$ and $T_N(y) \geq \alpha$, so $x \cdot (y \cdot z), y \in U(T_N; \alpha) \neq \emptyset$. By assumption, we have $U(T_N; \alpha)$ is a UP-ideal of X and so $x \cdot z \in U(T_N; \alpha)$. Thus $T_N(x \cdot z) \geq \alpha = \min\{T_N(x \cdot (y \cdot z)), T_N(y)\}$.

Let $x \in X$. Then $I_N(x) \in [-1, 0]$. Choose $\beta = I_N(x)$. Thus $I_N(x) \leq \beta$, so $x \in L(I_N; \beta) \neq \emptyset$. By assumption, we have $L(I_N; \beta)$ is a UP-ideal of X and so $0 \in L(I_N; \beta)$. Thus $I_N(0) \leq \beta = I_N(x)$. Next, let $x, y, z \in X$. Then $I_N(x \cdot (y \cdot z)), I_N(y) \in [-1, 0]$. Choose $\beta = \max\{I_N(x \cdot (y \cdot z)), I_N(y)\}$. Thus $I_N(x \cdot (y \cdot z)) \leq \beta$ and $I_N(y) \leq \beta$, so $x \cdot (y \cdot z), y \in L(I_N; \beta) \neq \emptyset$. By assumption, we have $L(I_N; \beta)$ is a UP-ideal of X and so $x \cdot z \in L(I_N; \beta)$. Thus $I_N(x \cdot z) \leq \beta = \max\{I_N(x \cdot (y \cdot z)), I_N(y)\}$.

Let $x \in X$. Then $F_N(x) \in [-1, 0]$. Choose $\gamma = F_N(x)$. Thus $F_N(x) \geq \gamma$, so $x \in U(F_N; \gamma) \neq \emptyset$. By assumption, we have $U(F_N; \gamma)$ is a UP-ideal of X and so $0 \in U(F_N; \gamma)$. Thus $F_N(0) \geq \gamma = F_N(x)$. Next, let $x, y, z \in X$. Then $F_N(x \cdot (y \cdot z)), F_N(y) \in [-1, 0]$. Choose $\gamma = \min\{F_N(x \cdot (y \cdot z)), F_N(y)\}$. Thus $F_N(x \cdot (y \cdot z)) \geq \gamma$ and $F_N(y) \geq \gamma$, so $x \cdot (y \cdot z), y \in U(F_N; \gamma) \neq \emptyset$. By assumption, we have $U(F_N; \gamma)$ is a UP-ideal of X and so $x \cdot z \in U(F_N; \gamma)$. Thus $F_N(x \cdot z) \geq \gamma = \min\{F_N(x \cdot (y \cdot z)), F_N(y)\}$.

Therefore, X_N is a special neutrosophic $\mathcal{N}$ -UP-ideal of X .

Definition 6.5 Let X_N be a neutrosophic $\mathcal{N}$ -structure over X . For $\alpha, \beta, \gamma \in [-1, 0]$, the sets

$$ULU_{X_N}(\alpha, \beta, \gamma) = \{x \in X \mid T_N \geq \alpha, I_N \leq \beta, F_N \geq \gamma\},$$

$$LUL_{X_N}(\alpha, \beta, \gamma) = \{x \in X \mid T_N \leq \alpha, I_N \geq \beta, F_N \leq \gamma\},$$

$$E_{X_N}(\alpha, \beta, \gamma) = \{x \in X \mid T_N = \alpha, I_N = \beta, F_N = \gamma\}$$

are called a $ULU - (\alpha, \beta, \gamma)$ -level subset, an $LUL - (\alpha, \beta, \gamma)$ -level subset, and an $E - (\alpha, \beta, \gamma)$ -level subset of X_N , respectively. Then we see that

$$ULU_{X_N}(\alpha, \beta, \gamma) = U(T_N; \alpha) \cap L(I_N; \beta) \cap U(F_N; \gamma),$$

$$LUL_{X_N}(\alpha, \beta, \gamma) = L(T_N; \alpha) \cap U(I_N; \beta) \cap L(F_N; \gamma),$$

$$E_{X_N}(\alpha, \beta, \gamma) = E(T_N; \alpha) \cap E(I_N; \beta) \cap E(F_N; \gamma).$$

Corollary 6.6 A neutrosophic $\mathcal{N}^c$ -structure X_N over X is a neutrosophic $\mathcal{N}^c$ -UP-subalgebra of X if and only if for all $\alpha, \beta, \gamma \in [-1, 0]$, $LUL_{X_N}(\alpha, \beta, \gamma)$ is a UP-subalgebra of X where $LUL_{X_N}(\alpha, \beta, \gamma)$ is nonempty.

Proof. It is straightforward by Theorem 4.2.

Corollary 6.7 A neutrosophic $\mathcal{N}^c$ -structure X_N over X is a neutrosophic $\mathcal{N}^c$ -near UP-filter of X if and only if for all $\alpha, \beta, \gamma \in [-1, 0]$, $LUL_{X_N}(\alpha, \beta, \gamma)$ is a near UP-filter of X where $LUL_{X_N}(\alpha, \beta, \gamma)$ is nonempty.

Proof. It is straightforward by Theorem 4.3.

Corollary 6.8 A neutrosophic $\mathcal{N}^c$ -structure X_N over X is a neutrosophic $\mathcal{N}^c$ -UP-filter of X if and only if for all $\alpha, \beta, \gamma \in [-1, 0]$, $LUL_{X_N}(\alpha, \beta, \gamma)$ is a UP-filter of X where $LUL_{X_N}(\alpha, \beta, \gamma)$ is nonempty.

Proof. It is straightforward by Theorem 4.4.

Corollary 6.9 A neutrosophic $\mathcal{N}^c$ -structure X_N over X is a neutrosophic $\mathcal{N}^c$ -UP-ideal of X if and only if for all $\alpha, \beta, \gamma \in [-1, 0]$, $LUL_{X_N}(\alpha, \beta, \gamma)$ is a UP-ideal of X where $LUL_{X_N}(\alpha, \beta, \gamma)$ is nonempty.

Proof. It is straightforward by Theorem 4.5.

Corollary 6.10 A neutrosophic $\mathcal{N}^c$ -structure X_N over X is a neutrosophic $\mathcal{N}^c$ -strongly UP-ideal of X if and only if $E(T_N, T_N(0)) = X$, $E(I_N, I_N(0)) = X$, and $E(F_N, F_N(0)) = X$.

Proof. It is straightforward by Theorem 4.6.

Corollary 6.11 A neutrosophic $\mathcal{N}^c$ -structure X_N over X is a special neutrosophic $\mathcal{N}^c$ -UP-subalgebra of X if and only if for all $\alpha, \beta, \gamma \in [-1, 0]$, $ULU_{X_N}(\alpha, \beta, \gamma)$ is a UP-subalgebra of X where $ULU_{X_N}(\alpha, \beta, \gamma)$ is nonempty.

Proof. It is straightforward by Theorem 6.1.

Corollary 6.12 A neutrosophic $\mathcal{N}^c$ -structure X_N over X is a special neutrosophic $\mathcal{N}^c$ -near UP-filter of X if and only if for all $\alpha, \beta, \gamma \in [-1, 0]$, $ULU_{X_N}(\alpha, \beta, \gamma)$ is a near UP-filter of X where $ULU_{X_N}(\alpha, \beta, \gamma)$ is nonempty.

Proof. It is straightforward by Theorem 6.2.

Corollary 6.13 A neutrosophic $\mathcal{N}$ -structure X_N over X is a special neutrosophic $\mathcal{N}$ -UP-filter of X if and only if for all $\alpha, \beta, \gamma \in [-1, 0]$, $ULU_{X_N}(\alpha, \beta, \gamma)$ is a UP-filter of X where $ULU_{X_N}(\alpha, \beta, \gamma)$ is nonempty.

Proof. It is straightforward by Theorem 6.3.

Corollary 6.14 A neutrosophic $\mathcal{N}$ -structure X_N over X is a special neutrosophic $\mathcal{N}$ -UP-ideal of X if and only if for all $\alpha, \beta, \gamma \in [-1, 0]$, $ULU_{X_N}(\alpha, \beta, \gamma)$ is a UP-ideal of X where $ULU_{X_N}(\alpha, \beta, \gamma)$ is nonempty.

Proof. It is straightforward by Theorem 6.4.

7. Conclusions

In this paper, we have introduced the notions of (special) neutrosophic N -UP-subalgebras, (special) neutrosophic N -near UP-filters, (special) neutrosophic N -UP-filters, (special) neutrosophic N -UP-ideals, and (special) neutrosophic N -strongly UP-ideals of UP-algebras and investigated some of their important properties. Then we have that the notion of (special) neutrosophic N -UP-subalgebras is a generalization of (special) neutrosophic N -near UP-filters, (special) neutrosophic N -near UP-filters is a generalization of (special) neutrosophic N -UP-filters, (special) neutrosophic N -UP-filters is a generalization of (special) neutrosophic N -UP-ideals, and (special) neutrosophic N -UP-ideals is a generalization of (special) neutrosophic N -strongly UP-ideals. Moreover, we obtain that (special) neutrosophic N -strongly UP-ideals and constant neutrosophic N -structures coincide.

In our future study, we will apply these notion/results to other type of neutrosophic N -structures in UP-algebras. Also, we will study the soft set theory/cubic set theory of such neutrosophic N -structures.

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